

An Open Source, Parallel, and Distributed Web-Based Probabilistic Risk Assessment Platform to Support Real Time Nuclear Power Plant Risk-Informed Operational Decisions

Milestone Report

Task 3: Testing and Benchmarking for Serial and Parallel Improvements

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Executive Summary

This milestone report serves as a cornerstone in demonstrating how improvements can be made to a Probabilistic Risk Assessment (PRA) tool. The improvement strategy was applied to both SAPHSOLVE and SCRAM, with the potential to be extended to other quantification engines with minimal effort.

Additionally, a testing environment for code improvements was established for SCRAM, ensuring that each implementation is thoroughly tested before releasing updated versions. Finally, an in-depth literature review on multi-hazard PRA models was completed, which will support our future efforts in developing multi-hazard PRA models.

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Disclaimer

The content of this report is largely a combination of various project outcomes, including conference papers, a master's thesis, and a Ph.D. dissertation.

Outcomes of the Project

The project contributes to the research environment in various ways, and the outcomes are listed below for reference. In addition to the listed outcomes, two journal papers are ready for submission, and one report covering the SAPHIRE post-processing engine is under review. Furthermore, North Carolina State University and Idaho National Laboratory have established a highly efficient collaborative environment.

1.1 Conference Papers

1. Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models [1]
2. Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM [2]
3. Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models [3]
4. Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment [4]
5. Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX [5]
6. Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement [6]
7. Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts [7]
8. Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence [8]
9. Towards a Deep-Learning Based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis [9]

1.2 Journal Papers

1. A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants [10]

1.3 Reports

1. Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver [11]

1.4 Master's Thesis

1. Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHSOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM [12]

1.5 Ph.D. Dissertation

1. Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Optimization and Parallel Computing [13]

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
DOM	Document Object Model
DPPL	Delphi Parallel Programming Library
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
INL	Idaho National Laboratory
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MCUB	Min Cut Upper Bound
MEF	Model Exchange Framework
NARSIS	Natural External Hazards Including Seismic
PRA	Probabilistic Risk Assessment
PSA	Probabilistic Safety Assessment
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 Testing and Benchmarking for Serial and Parallel Improvements

1.1 Overview of Report

This report marks a significant milestone in the overall project. As a reminder, the project consists of five main tasks, which are outlined below. This milestone report presents the outcomes of the third task:

- Task 1: Literature review, benchmarking, and profiling of current PRA tools
- Task 2: Design and implementation
- Task 3: Testing and benchmarking for serial and parallel improvements
- Task 4: Application to real world PRA models
- Task 5: Verification and documentation

The remainder of the report is structured as follows: Section 1.2 introduces the various tests conducted during the development and improvement phases. Section 1.3 presents the improvements made to SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE. Section 1.4 reviews various works on multi-hazards PRA model development.

1.2 Source-code Testing

Static type checking has been integrated across the entire codebase of the OpenPRA web application. The frontend is built using React [14], and the backend is developed with the NestJS [15] framework, both of which are written in TypeScript. Additionally, the scram-node engine is implemented in C++. Since both TypeScript [16] and C++ are statically typed languages, any type-related errors are caught during compilation, before the code is executed. Additionally, an external library called Nestia [17] has been used for runtime type checking, ensuring that no invalid or malicious input or output can be passed to OpenPRA or its users.

Beyond validating data input and output, it is crucial to verify that:

- All the components and features of OpenPRA function as intended
- The engine, frontend, backend, and database components are properly coupled
- The web app behaves as expected
- The app remains stable when new features are introduced unless breaking changes are made

- The app can handle many concurrent users and requests or heavy loads

To meet these requirements, five types of tests have been developed for the OpenPRA app:

1. Unit tests,
2. Functional tests,
3. Regression tests,
4. End-to-end tests, and
5. Stress tests.

Before diving into the implementation, it's important to clarify the definitions and purposes of each test type:

Unit tests focus on verifying the correctness of individual components or functions in isolation. They test small, specific parts of the code to ensure they behave as expected. These tests may involve minimal data mocking.

Functional tests assess the application's features and functionalities to ensure they meet the specified requirements. These tests typically simulate user interactions to verify that the system responds correctly. Functional tests may involve extensive data and component mocking, as they also check whether the components are properly coupled.

Regression tests are designed to detect any unintended changes or bugs introduced by new code or modifications. They help maintain the application's stability over time. Unless major breaking changes are introduced, regression tests are useful for ensuring the integrity of the code.

End-to-end tests evaluate the entire application workflow by simulating real-world scenarios from start to finish. They ensure that all components work together seamlessly and that the application functions correctly as a whole. In these tests, only the database is mocked, while all other components are used in their entirety to observe their actual behavior in a production environment.

Stress tests assess the application's performance and stability under extreme conditions. These tests subject the system to high loads or resource constraints to identify potential bottlenecks and ensure the app can handle peak usage scenarios. The actual database is used in this case to understand the limitations of all parts of the application.

1.2.1 Unit Testing

Unit tests have been used to verify the core components of the frontend, such as clickable buttons, menus, sidebars, navigation bars, breadcrumbs, and text fields. These tests ensure that the Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) Document Object Model (DOM) is correctly manipulated when users interact with the frontend. On the backend, unit tests focus on individual methods within the controllers. Controllers are responsible for determining the route, Uniform Resource Locator (URL) through which data will be passed between the frontend and the database. Unit tests ensure that the input parameters and Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) responses of each controller method behave as expected. In the distributed system, unit tests ensure that quantification jobs are correctly queued in the job queues. Unit tests are written using the Jest [18] library in all these cases. In the case of scram-node engine, unit tests written using the Boost [19] library are used to evaluate individual methods. For instance, testing the *parseArguments()* method and the *settings* class helps verify whether the quantification configurations are correctly received or if there are any errors in the settings. For example, a user might attempt to use both the BDD and ZBDD algorithms simultaneously, which is not allowed.

1.2.2 Functional Testing

Functional tests have been done to verify the functionality of comparatively larger frontend components, including the signup and sign-in forms, user profile, web-editors that are used for creating fault tree, event tree, event sequence diagram, and Bayesian network, among others. Since functional testing also assesses component coupling, it checks whether the web editor is making appropriate Application Programming Interface (API) fetch requests after form submission or after modifying a model in the web-editor. On the backend, functional tests ensure that services are properly connected to controllers to receive requests from the web editor and verify that they can communicate with the database through business logic. They also verify whether the backend can connect to the job broker and whether worker instances can consume jobs from the queues. Functional testing for the scram-node engine ensures that input parameters are correctly passed from a parent method to child methods through proper subroutine calls. For instance, an erroneous fault tree input is given to the *main()* method to verify if the *processInputFile()* method catches and throws the error, confirming correct subroutine execution.

1.2.3 Regression Testing

Regression tests have been done for functionalities that are expected to remain unchanged unless a major update occurs. For instance, regardless of how icons or symbols are designed in the web editor for fault trees, event trees, or Bayesian networks,

the models created in these editors must always generate a JSON schema that follows the OpenPRA-Model Exchange Framework (MEF) standard when sent via API requests. The same rule applies for the scram-node engine, it must consistently follow the MEF-Extensible Markup Language (XML) schema for both input and output files. Unless the MEF schema changes, the frontend and the engine should consistently produce the same input model and quantification result respectively.

1.2.4 End-to-end Testing

For the frontend, the end-to-end test covers the entire user journey, starting from account creation to building multiple models in the web editor, configuring quantification settings, and finally pressing the *quantify* button. It also simulates the user logging in and viewing the list of previously created models. On the backend, end-to-end tests encompass scenarios from user authentication to receiving quantification requests from the frontend and processing the models using the scram-node engine wrapper methods. Additionally, it simulates other operations like fetching, updating, or deleting models from the database. In the distributed system simulation, the backend connects to the job broker, queues the jobs, processes and quantifies them, and sends the results to the database via a separate queue. In all the frontend, backend, and distributed system cases, the actual applications are launched using either Playwright [20] or SuperTest [21], and predefined steps are executed to mimic user actions, ensuring the app functions as expected as a whole.

1.2.5 Stress Testing

Stress testing primarily focuses on the backend, the database, the distributed system and the scram-node engine. It involves two key parameters: the number of concurrent users and the number of actions each user performs in a given cycle. Essentially, the end-to-end tests described earlier are repeated over numerous cycles to simulate the behavior of heavy concurrent user load. The number of end-to-end tests corresponds to the number of actions a user would take, and these actions are executed in a loop for each concurrent user. Stress tests help establish the baseline load capacity for the backend, job queues, database, and scram-node quantification, with clearly defined performance metrics such as requests per second, average response time under heavy load, and the maximum number of requests the backend, database, distributed system, and scram-node engine can handle.

Code snippets from several of these test files and their corresponding test coverage results have been presented at the end of the report in Appendix F in Section 3.6.

1.3 Improvement Methodology for a PRA Quantification Engine – Applied to SCRAM and SAPH SOLVE

1.3.1 Overview of Improvement Methodology

The enhancement methodology, as outlined in the proposed success tree, emerges as a result of the diagnostic study. This is typically achieved through one of two approaches: optimization or parallel computing.

As depicted in Figure 1, the improvement strategy is subdivided into seven categories, each representing a potential area for enhancement. The goal is to achieve at least one improvement for each child node, either on SCRAM or SAPH SOLVE. The target is to optimize the cut set generation algorithm and post-processing engine for SAPH SOLVE and optimizing the storage of cut sets, probability calculations, and reporting results, as well as parallelizing calculations such as probability, uncertainty, and importance measurement for SCRAM.

Figure 1. Improvement strategy of a PRA tool as a success tree format.

1.3.2 SAPH SOLVE Improvements Through Code Optimization

Standard profiling revealed that both function A and function B need improvement. The selected strategy involves using parallel computing to enhance function A and rewriting function B for better performance.

Initially, the module containing function A was rewritten to facilitate parallel implementation. The proposed approach involves utilizing the Delphi Parallel Programming Library (DPPL) [22]. However, due to SAPH SOLVE not being open source and the conclusion of the collaboration with the SAPHIRE team, the parallel computing capability could not be fully realized. Nevertheless, the module has been prepared for parallel execution to enhance the performance of function A and ultimately SAPH SOLVE.

Concurrently, another optimization strategy for SAPH SOLVE involves updating the module housing function B, which was originally written for a 32-bit architecture. The proposed strategy includes transitioning the architecture to 64-bit, thereby enabling a larger address space, enhancing performance, and ensuring SAPH SOLVE can leverage future advancements in hardware and software technologies.

The updates encompass changes in data types, handling of pointers, and addressing any potential issues related to memory allocation. Additionally, function calls are updated to align with the new architecture. Following the architectural changes, SAPH SOLVE is executed with the same fault tree (ft-310) using various truncation sizes, and the results are presented in Table 1. On average, a 1.43x speedup is achieved.

Figure 2 illustrates the comparison of computation time before and after the optimization of the SetLib module. Despite the optimization, the exponential behavior dependent on truncation size is still observed.

Table 1. SAPH SOLVE computation time before and after optimization for ft-310 input file.

#	Truncation Size of MCS	SetLib-32bit [sec]	SetLib-64bit [sec]	Speed Up
1	15	70.42	56.67	1.24
2	16	259.35	179.03	1.45
3	17	1,087.66	872.75	1.25
4	18	4,497.45	2,963.55	1.52
5	19	20,310.73	12,181.31	1.67
6	20	82,783.48	56,220.37	1.47

Figure 2. SAPH SOLVE computation time before and after optimization.

However, after optimization, SAPH SOLVE was re-profiled with the same fault tree, resulting in a significant decrease in the contribution of function B and a corresponding increase in the contribution of function A, as expected. Details are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. SAPH SOLVE MOCSU MCUB Vtune profiling results after optimization efforts.

Truncation Size	Function	CPU Time [sec]	Percentage Contribution to Whole Run [%]
16	A	197.638	58.7
	B	34.698	10.3
18	B	1137.573	34.2
	A	836.266	25.10
20	B	25000.019	57.80
	C	3459.037	8.0
	A	2673.911	6.20

As part of future work, the goal is to leverage parallel computing for both function A and function B to further enhance the performance of SAPH SOLVE.

1.3.3 SAPHISOLVE Post-Processing Engine Development

Accident sequence cut sets generated during PRA often necessitate manipulation to address specific modeling concerns, such as post-accident scenarios, common-cause failure modeling, and the removal of mutually exclusive events. Rather than re-quantifying the entire model for each manipulation, which is expensive computation, the post-processing engine in SAPHIRE empowers users to manipulate generated cut sets efficiently by defining rules.

The initial implementation of cut set manipulation in SAPHIRE dates back to 1996 and was known as the recovery engine [23]. To utilize the post-processing engine, users create a Rule File using the SAPHIRE GUI. This Rule File comprises numerous if-else statements followed by the actions. Depending on the conditions defined by the user in the Rule File, the SAPHIRE post-processing engine adeptly updates generated cut sets and associated failure probabilities for each sequence.

While the current post-processing engine is seamlessly integrated with other engines in the SAPHIRE API and functions effectively, the SAPHIRE team places a strong emphasis on maintainability. Given the rapidly changing landscape of computational resources, programming languages, and environments, the team is dedicated to adopting the most recent technologies to ensure the sustained functionality of SAPHIRE, its SPAR models, and associated components.

1.3.3.1 Overview of SAPHIRE Post-Processing Engine

For a comprehensive understanding of Rule Files, including detailed explanations, keywords, and examples, readers are directed to refer to the SAPHIRE Manual Volume 3 [24].

```

1. |Rule File Example
2. if A * B +C * D +E then
3. deleteroot;
4.
5. elseif F * G
6. then
7. deleteevent = G;
8.
9. elseif H
10. then
11. addevent = F;
12.
13. end if
14.
15. |end of Rule File

```

A Rule File comprises various statements and actions as seen on the left. In the provided example, symbols are used to denote specific instructions: "|" represents a comment, "*" indicates an *AND* operation, and "+" signifies an *OR* operation. The rule defined in the Rule File instructs the engine to take certain actions when specific basic events are identified within the cut set list.

For instance, if the engine encounters a cut set with the events (*A AND B*) *OR* (*C AND D*) *OR E*, it is directed to remove these cut sets from the list. Following this removal, the engine recalculates the failure probability using the remaining cut sets. If the specified events are not found, the engine proceeds to the next "else if" statement for further evaluation.

The new post-processing engine has been completely re-built from scratch. It encompasses five core functions, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Post-processing engine schematic representation.

- **JSCUTIN File Parser:** This function parses the JSCUTIN file, which contains the cut set list for each sequence along with basic event information.
- **Rule File Parser:** The Rule File parser reads the Rule File and converts it into a lightweight, easy-to-manipulate JSON object.
- **Post-processor:** The post-processor updates the JSCUTIN file based on the rules provided in the Rule File.
- **Probability Calculator:** This function re-calculates the failure probability for each sequence list, considering previous truncation values.
- **JSCUTIN Writer:** The JSCUTIN writer writes out the updated JSCUTIN file in JSON format.

1.3.3.2 Implementation Details

As illustrated in Figure 3, the JSCUTIN file and rule file are utilized as inputs to the post-processing engine. The following files from generic PWR model [25] are provided in the appendices to provide further insights:

- The abbreviated ACC JSCUTIN file is presented in Appendix A, containing only the necessary details.
- The post-processed ACC JSCUTIN file is included in Appendix B.
- The rule file can be found in Appendix C.

- The proposed rule file JSON schema is provided in Appendix D.
- The parsed and JSON-formatted generic PWR rule file is available in Appendix E.

The JSCUTIN file is a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file containing SAPHSOLVE engine quantification results, along with basic event information. As discussed, users may wish to update the quantification results without re-quantifying the entire PRA model. To achieve this, users create a rule file to specify updates to the cut sets. The post-processing engine parses the JSCUTIN file and the rule file, performs the necessary actions specified in the rule file, modifies the cut set list, accordingly, recalculates the probability using Min Cut Upper Bound (MCUB), and outputs a new JSCUTIN file.

```

1. {
2.   "generalpostprocessingrules": {
3.
4.     "conditionlist": [
5.       {
6.         "rulesection":1,
7.         "conditionid":1,
8.         "conditiontype": "if OR else-if, OR else ",
9.         "cutsetlist": [
10.          {
11.            "event": []
12.          }
13.        ],
14.        "actionlist": [
15.          {
16.            "addconvoevent": [],
17.            "addevent": [],
18.            "copycutset": [],
19.            "copyroot": [],
20.            "deleteevent": [],
21.            "deleteroot": [],
22.            "newcutset": [],
23.            "recovery": []
24.          }
25.        ]
26.      }
27.    ]
28.  }
29. }

```

Figure 4. Conversion rule JSON schema

As depicted in Figure 4, the conversion of the rule file into JSON format enables portability and efficient communication with various engines or databases. The parsed original rule file is transformed into two distinct lists: the *condition list* and the *action list*. In the provided example of the basic demo rule file and the one in Appendix C, users define conditional

statements related to basic events and specify actions to be taken within the generated cut sets. The action list encompasses all possible actions that users may expect, regardless of the length or complexity of the conditions, which are saved as JSON objects.

The post-processing engine is implemented in C# since the SAPHIRE developer team has expressed a preference for C#, and the team is experienced in this programming language. It's worth noting that the JSCUTIN file or rule file can be directly fed into the post-processing engine, or the engine can retrieve input files from a database when needed.

As illustrated in Appendix C, the rule file contains assigned basic event names, whereas the JSCUTIN file includes cut sets that are masked. The post-processing engine is capable of unmasking the cut set information during processing and masking it again when providing the updated JSCUTIN file. This masking technique is employed for faster manipulation.

The allocation of 32 bits is distributed as follows, also illustrated in Figure 5.

- Event number from 0 to 17
- Phase information from 18 to 24
- Model type from 25 to 29
- Basic event tag on bit 30
- Complement information on bit 31

Masking	Complement	Basic Event Tag	Model Type	Phase	Event Number
Bit	1	0	9 8 7 6 5	4 3 2 1 0 9 8	7 6 5 4 3 2 1 0 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1 0

Figure 5. Bit set distribution of masked basic event number.

As an example, let's consider a basic event number represented in decimal as 33816579, which corresponds to an event number of 3, phase of 1, and model of 1, as demonstrated in Figure 6.

Masking	Complement	Basic Event Tag	Model Type	Phase	Event Number
Bit	0	0	0 0 0 0 1	0 0 0 0 0 0 1	0 1 1

Figure 6. Bit set distribution of simple example.

1.3.3.3 Results & Discussions

As a result, the post-processing implementation has been validated and tested with various models, either by directly feeding the post-processing engine or by reading input files from the database.

As a demonstration, ACC FT model provided in Appendix A is considered. The JSCUTIN file includes 78 cut sets with a probability value of 6.10696E-2.

The rule provided in Appendix C is designed for the ACC FT model, aiming to remove the LOCA related events from the cut sets. Applying this rule results in 2 cut sets with a recalculated probability of 1.21eE-7, as detailed in Appendix E.

The Rule File representation related to the ACC FT model can take various forms, such as the basic event name representation, basic event decimal representation, or basic event number representation. In any case, it is successfully parsed and fed into the post-processing engine along with the JSCUTIN file. Table 3 represents various form of the same rule.

Table 3. Different representation of same rule file for demonstration purpose.

Representation	Rule File
Name Representation	<pre> 1. if ((~IE-LLOCA + ~IE-MLOCA + ~IE-SLOCA) * 2. (RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL2 + 3. RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL3 + 4. RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL4 + 5. RCS-LOCA-CL2 * RCS-LOCA-CL3 + 6. RCS-LOCA-CL2 * RCS-LOCA-CL4 + 7. RCS-LOCA-CL3 * RCS-LOCA-CL4)) then 8. DeleteRoot; 9. endif </pre>
Decimal Representation	<pre> 1. if 33816688 * 33816689 + 2. 33816688 * 33816690 + 3. 33816688 * 33816691 + 4. 33816689 * 33816690 + 5. 33816689 * 33816691 + 6. 33816690 * 33816691 then 7. Deleteroot; 8. endif </pre>
Number Representation with Tag	<pre> 1. if ((~<BE>68</BE> + ~<BE>489</BE> + ~<BE>3418</BE>) *(<BE>112</BE> * <BE>113</BE> + 2. <BE>112</BE> * <BE>114</BE> + 3. <BE>112</BE> * <BE>115</BE> + 4. <BE>113</BE> * <BE>114</BE> + 5. <BE>113</BE> * <BE>115</BE> + 6. <BE>114</BE> * <BE>115</BE>)) then 7. DeleteRoot; 8. endif </pre>
Number Representation without Tag	<pre> 1. if ((~68 + ~489 + ~3418) * 2. (112 * 113 + 3. 112 * 114 + 4. 112 * 115 + 5. 113 * 114 + 6. 113 * 115 + </pre>

```
7. 114 * 115 )) then
8. DeleteRoot;
9. endif
```

1.3.3.4 Conclusion

The proposed diagnostics and improvement methodology not only serves to enhance the quantification engine but also drives all improvement efforts within a PRA tool. The development of the SAPHIRE post-processing engine exemplifies the outcome of this methodology. It is a significant achievement that underscores the inevitability of improvement when diagnostics are accurate.

The newly developed SAPHIRE post-processing engine has been created and thoroughly tested with various models. As previously mentioned, the post-processing engine plays a critical role in PRA by addressing specific modeling concerns, such as post-accident scenarios, common-cause failure modeling, and the removal of mutually exclusive events. Instead of recomputing the entire model for each manipulation, which is a computationally expensive process, the post-processing engine in SAPHIRE empowers users to efficiently manipulate generated cut sets by defining rules.

1.3.4 SCRAM Improvement Through Code Optimization and Parallel Computing

It's identified that SCRAM can be enhanced by focusing on cut set generation, calculations, and reporting the results. In this work, our focus lies on improving calculations and reporting the results, leaving the remaining improvements for future endeavors.

To enhance probability calculations, we begin by altering the data structure used to store cut sets from ZBDD to a vector of vectors. Storing cut sets in this manner allows for efficient iteration through the cut sets during the calculation of failure probability. Furthermore, we parallelize the probability calculation step using OpenMP. Additionally, we employ OpenMP to parallelize importance measurement and uncertainty calculation processes.

In terms of reporting results, optimization efforts involve copying all generated cut sets into a vector of vectors, which facilitates faster iteration. These enhancements contribute to the overall improvement of SCRAM and pave the way for future advancements in PRA tool development.

The enhancement study was conducted on a same system as in diagnostics study, a Dell Inc. OptiFlex 7060 machine equipped with 16 GiB of memory. The system features an Intel Core i7-8700 CPU clocked at 3.20 GHz with 12 processors [26]. Additionally, it boasts a capacious 2.0 TB disk capacity and operates on a 64-bit Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS operating system.

1.3.4.1 Results and Discussions

The initial improvement efforts are focused on probability calculation, considered a future investment since probability calculation itself does not dominate the entire process. However, probability calculation may be revisited during any post-processing actions. The original and revised code snippets are presented in Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively. As indicated in Table 4, about 3-fold speed-up for the loop is achieved, albeit with overhead incurred while copying ZBDD data structures into a vector of vectors.

```

1. double McubCalculator::Calculate(
2.     const Zbdd& cut_sets, const Pdag::IndexMap<double>& p_vars) noexcept {
3.     double m = 1;
4.     for (const std::vector<int>& cut_set : cut_sets) {
5.         m *= 1 - CutSetProbabilityCalculator::Calculate(cut_set, p_vars);
6.     }
7.     return 1 - m;
8. }

```

Figure 7. Original (serial) MCUB probability calculation code snippet.

```

1. double McubCalculator::Calculate(const Zbdd& cut_sets, const Pdag::IndexMap<double>& p_vars)
noexcept {
2.     double m = 1;
3.     #pragma omp parallel for reduction(*:m)
4.     for (auto it = cut_sets.begin(); it != cut_sets.end() ; ++it) {
5.         const std::vector<int>& cut_set = *it;
6.         m *= 1 - CutSetProbabilityCalculator::Calculate(cut_set, p_vars);
7.     }
8.     return 1 - m;
9. }

```

Figure 8. Revised (parallel) MCUB probability calculation code snippet.

Table 4. Probability calculation improvements using three most time-consuming models.

Input	Conversion-Serial	Loop-Serial	MCUB-Serial	Probability-Serial	Conversion-Parallel	Loop-Parallel	MCUB-Parallel	Probability-Parallel	Loop Speedup
edfpa14b	1.26E+04	7.05E+02	1.33E+04	1.43E+04	1.26E+04	2.30E+02	1.28E+04	1.38E+04	3.07
edfpa14o	1.20E+04	7.28E+02	1.27E+04	1.37E+04	1.20E+04	2.29E+02	1.22E+04	1.32E+04	3.19
edfpa14q	1.18E+04	6.97E+02	1.25E+04	1.35E+04	1.20E+04	2.30E+02	1.22E+04	1.32E+04	3.03

Explanations about the table:

- All units are in milliseconds.
- Conversion: Refers to the time taken for copying cut sets from the ZBDD data structure to a vector of vectors.
- Loop: Indicates the time spent within the loop during the calculation process.
- MCUB: Represents the time taken for the probability calculation using the MCUB approximation method.
- Probability: Represents the total time taken for the entire probability calculation process.

The second improvement aims to optimize the reporting of results. The original and revised code snippets are presented in Figure 9 and Figure 10 respectively. The figures also illustrate how the logger is implemented in the code to measure the time. As shown in Table 5, the reporter class has been sped up by a factor of up to 3.04, with a minimum speedup of 0.79. The maximum speedup occurs with a large number of cut sets, while the minimum is observed with a smaller number of cut sets. For example, the model edfpa14p demonstrates the maximum speed up with a number of products exceeding a hundred million, whereas the minimum speedup comes from the ftr10 model, which has 305 cut sets. The speedup in the reporter class comes with overhead since the cut sets are copied into a vector of vectors before processing; however, in this case, the overhead is not significant. Additionally, the speedup in the reporter contributes to an overall speedup of up to 2.41 with a minimum of 0.83 in folding.

```

1. void Reporter::ReportResults(const core::RiskAnalysis::Result::Id& id,
2.                             const core::FaultTreeAnalysis& fta,
3.                             const core::ProbabilityAnalysis* prob_analysis,
4.                             xml::StreamElement* results) {
5.     TIMER(DEBUG2, "Reporting products");
6.     xml::StreamElement sum_of_products = results->AddChild("sum-of-products");
7.     scram::PutId(id, &sum_of_products);
8.
9.     std::string warning = fta.warnings();
10.    if (prob_analysis && prob_analysis->warnings().empty() == false)
11.        warning += (warning.empty() ? "" : "; ") + prob_analysis->warnings();
12.    if (!warning.empty())
13.        sum_of_products.SetAttribute("warning", warning);
14.
15.    sum_of_products
16.        .SetAttribute("basic-events", fta.products().product_events().size())
17.        .SetAttribute("products", fta.products().size());
18.
19.    if (prob_analysis)
20.        sum_of_products.SetAttribute("probability", prob_analysis->p_total());
21.
22.    if (fta.products().empty() == false) {
23.        sum_of_products.SetAttribute(
24.            "distribution",
25.            boost::join(fta.products().distribution() |
26.                        boost::adaptors::transformed(
27.                            [](int number) { return std::to_string(number); }),
28.            " ");
29.    }
30.    double sum = 0;
31.    CLOCK(sum_prob_reporter);
32.
33.    if (prob_analysis) {
34.        for (const core::Product& product_set : fta.products())
35.            sum += product_set.p();
36.    }
37.
38.    LOG(DEBUG1)<<"Sum of probabilities in reporter completed in "<<DUR(sum_prob_reporter);
39.    CLOCK(fta_product_reporter);
40.
41.    for (const core::Product& product_set : fta.products()) {
42.        xml::StreamElement product = sum_of_products.AddChild("product");
43.        product.SetAttribute("order", product_set.order());
44.        if (prob_analysis) {
45.            double prob = product_set.p();
46.            product.SetAttribute("probability", prob);
47.            if (sum != 0)
48.                product.SetAttribute("contribution", prob / sum);
49.        }
50.        for (const core::Literal& literal : product_set) {
51.            ReportLiteral(literal, &product);
52.        }
53.    }
54.    LOG(DEBUG1)<<"fta product reporter is completed in "<<DUR(fta_product_reporter);
55. }

```

Figure 9. Original (ZBDD data structure) reporting code snippet.

```

1. void Reporter::ReportResults(const core::RiskAnalysis::Result::Id& id,
2.                             const core::FaultTreeAnalysis& fta,
3.                             const core::ProbabilityAnalysis* prob_analysis,
4.                             xml::StreamElement* results) {
5.     TIMER(DEBUG2, "Reporting products");
6.     xml::StreamElement sum_of_products = results->AddChild("sum-of-products");
7.     scram::PutId(id, &sum_of_products);
8.
9.     std::string warning = fta.warnings();
10.    if (prob_analysis && prob_analysis->warnings().empty() == false)
11.        warning += (warning.empty() ? "" : "; ") + prob_analysis->warnings();
12.    if (!warning.empty())
13.        sum_of_products.SetAttribute("warning", warning);
14.
15.    sum_of_products
16.        .SetAttribute("basic-events", fta.products().product_events().size())
17.        .SetAttribute("products", fta.products().size());
18.
19.    if (prob_analysis)
20.        sum_of_products.SetAttribute("probability", prob_analysis->p_total());
21.
22.    if (fta.products().empty() == false) {
23.        sum_of_products.SetAttribute(
24.            "distribution",
25.            boost::join(fta.products().distribution() |
26.                        boost::adaptors::transformed(
27.                            [](int number) { return std::to_string(number); }),
28.            " ");
29.    }
30.    //optimization - copy products into vector of vector
31.    CLOCK(copy_original_products);
32.    const auto& originalProducts = fta.products();
33.    std::vector<core::Product> productsCopy(originalProducts.begin(), originalProducts.end());
34.    LOG(DEBUG1)<<"Original products are copied in a vector in "<<DUR(copy_original_products);
35.
36.    double sum = 0; // Sum of probabilities for contribution calculations.
37.    CLOCK(sum_prob_reporter);
38.
39.    if (prob_analysis) {
40.        #pragma omp parallel for reduction(+:sum) //schedule(dynamic)
41.        for (auto it = productsCopy.begin(); it != productsCopy.end(); ++it) {
42.            const core::Product& product_set = *it;
43.            sum += product_set.p();
44.        }
45.    }
46.    LOG(DEBUG1)<<"Sum of probabilities in reporter completed in "<<DUR(sum_prob_reporter);
47.    CLOCK(fta_product_reporter);
48.    //iterate through vector of vector
49.    for (auto it = productsCopy.begin(); it != productsCopy.end(); ++it) {
50.        const core::Product& product_set = *it;
51.        xml::StreamElement product = sum_of_products.AddChild("product");
52.        product.SetAttribute("order", product_set.order());
53.        if (prob_analysis) {
54.            double prob = product_set.p();
55.            product.SetAttribute("probability", prob);
56.            if (sum != 0)
57.                product.SetAttribute("contribution", prob / sum);
58.        }
59.
60.        for (const core::Literal& literal : product_set) {
61.            ReportLiteral(literal, &product);
62.        }
63.    }
64.    LOG(DEBUG1)<<"fta product reporter is completed in "<<DUR(fta_product_reporter);
65. }

```

Figure 10. Revised (vector data structure) reporting code snippet.

Table 5. Reporter improvements by optimization.

#	Input	Report-Ori	Whole-Ori	ZBDD-to-Vector	Report-Opt	Whole-Opt	Report-Speedup	Whole-Speedup
1	baobab1	9.99E+01	2.75E+02	1.38E+00	3.65E+01	2.14E+02	2.74	1.29
2	baobab2	9.27E+00	1.19E+01	9.50E-02	4.12E+00	6.77E+00	2.25	1.76
3	baobab3	5.13E+01	9.75E+01	1.15E+00	2.00E+01	6.74E+01	2.57	1.45
4	chinese	7.09E-01	1.16E+00	4.00E-02	7.32E-01	1.40E+00	0.97	0.83
5	das9201	1.98E+01	2.24E+01	8.13E-01	1.21E+01	1.54E+01	1.64	1.45
6	das9202	6.79E+01	7.40E+01	2.66E+00	2.42E+01	3.29E+01	2.81	2.25
7	das9203	2.66E+01	2.95E+01	1.23E+00	1.46E+01	1.86E+01	1.82	1.58
8	das9204	4.10E+01	4.46E+01	1.63E+00	1.50E+01	2.01E+01	2.73	2.22
9	das9205	3.16E+01	3.39E+01	1.17E+00	1.47E+01	1.81E+01	2.15	1.87
10	das9206	3.12E+01	3.54E+01	1.40E+00	1.71E+01	2.26E+01	1.83	1.56
11	das9207	3.71E+01	4.70E+01	1.80E+00	2.22E+01	3.48E+01	1.67	1.35
12	das9208	1.26E+01	2.09E+01	3.62E-01	6.68E+00	1.56E+01	1.89	1.34
13	edf9201	9.17E+02	9.87E+02	3.61E+01	5.02E+02	6.06E+02	1.83	1.63
14	edf9202	2.59E+02	2.90E+02	1.46E+01	1.16E+02	1.61E+02	2.24	1.80
15	edf9203	4.41E+04	5.38E+04	9.28E+02	1.84E+04	2.89E+04	2.40	1.86
16	edf9204	7.81E+04	8.68E+04	1.95E+03	2.94E+04	3.86E+04	2.65	2.25
17	edf9205	3.45E+01	3.95E+01	1.30E+00	1.81E+01	2.46E+01	1.91	1.61
18	edfpa14b	2.63E+05	2.77E+05	6.12E+03	9.92E+04	1.19E+05	2.65	2.33
19	edfpa14o	2.62E+05	2.75E+05	5.76E+03	9.77E+04	1.16E+05	2.68	2.37
20	edfpa14p	1.03E+03	4.73E+03	1.54E+01	3.40E+02	4.10E+03	3.04	1.15
21	edfpa14q	2.60E+05	2.81E+05	5.86E+03	1.03E+05	1.30E+05	2.52	2.17
22	edfpa14r	9.54E+02	8.82E+03	1.39E+01	3.14E+02	8.25E+03	3.04	1.07
23	edfpa15b	6.17E+03	6.57E+03	1.66E+02	2.54E+03	3.10E+03	2.43	2.12
24	edfpa15o	6.09E+03	6.61E+03	1.57E+02	2.49E+03	3.16E+03	2.44	2.09
25	edfpa15p	5.84E+01	2.15E+02	1.13E+00	2.32E+01	1.88E+02	2.52	1.15
26	edfpa15q	6.10E+03	7.10E+03	1.57E+02	2.53E+03	3.65E+03	2.41	1.94
27	edfpa15r	5.65E+01	4.12E+02	1.12E+00	2.13E+01	3.51E+02	2.65	1.17
28	elf9601	3.23E+02	3.64E+02	1.24E+01	1.30E+02	1.84E+02	2.49	1.98
29	ftr10	3.87E-01	1.47E+00	2.10E-02	4.91E-01	1.57E+00	0.79	0.94
30	isp9601	5.23E+02	5.64E+02	2.19E+01	2.38E+02	3.00E+02	2.20	1.88

Table 5 (continued).

31	isp9602	1.28E+04	1.36E+04	4.28E+02	4.48E+03	5.73E+03	2.85	2.38
32	isp9603	5.12E+00	6.79E+00	2.02E-01	3.18E+00	5.10E+00	1.61	1.33
33	isp9604	1.29E+03	1.40E+03	5.96E+01	6.45E+02	8.13E+02	2.00	1.72
34	isp9605	1.11E+01	1.34E+01	1.27E-01	4.90E+00	7.56E+00	2.27	1.77
35	isp9606	2.46E+00	3.33E+00	1.08E-01	1.72E+00	2.75E+00	1.43	1.21
36	isp9607	4.04E+02	4.34E+02	1.51E+01	1.35E+02	1.80E+02	2.99	2.41
37	jbd9601	2.31E+01	3.33E+01	1.19E+00	1.26E+01	2.40E+01	1.84	1.39

Explanations about the table:

- All units are in milliseconds.
- Report-Ori: Original reporting time.
- Whole-Ori: Whole solving time.
- ZBDD-to-Vector: Copy time from ZBDD to vector of vector.
- Report-Opt: Optimized reporting time.
- Whole-Opt: Optimized whole solving time.
- Report-Speedup: Reporter speed up.
- Whole-Speedup: Whole time speed up.

The third improvement involves parallelizing importance measurement and uncertainty calculation by implementing OpenMP in the most time-consuming loops. The original and revised code snippets for importance measurement calculations are presented in Figure 11 and Figure 12, for uncertainty calculations are presented in Figure 13 and Figure 14 respectively. Table 6 outlines all the improvements and compares the original and revised versions of the code in terms of time. For instance, the total runtime is reduced from 8,140 seconds to 1,810 seconds for the model edfpa14b.

```
1. void ImportanceAnalysis::Analyze() noexcept {
2.   CLOCK(imp_time);
3.   LOG(DEBUG3) << "Calculating importance factors...";
4.   double p_total = this->p_total();
5.   const std::vector<const mef::BasicEvent*>& basic_events =
6.     this->basic_events();
7.
8.   std::vector<int> occurrences = this->occurrences();
9.   for (int i = 0; i < basic_events.size(); ++i) {
10.    if (occurrences[i] == 0)
11.      continue;
12.    const mef::BasicEvent& event = *basic_events[i];
13.    double p_var = event.p();
14.    ImportanceFactors imp{};
15.    imp.occurrence = occurrences[i];
16.    imp.mif = this->CalculateMif(i);
17.    if (p_total != 0) {
18.      imp.cif = p_var * imp.mif / p_total;
19.      imp.raw = 1 + (1 - p_var) * imp.mif / p_total;
20.      imp.dif = p_var * imp.raw;
21.      if (p_total != p_var * imp.mif)
22.        imp.rrw = p_total / (p_total - p_var * imp.mif);
23.    }
24.    importance_.push_back({event, imp});
25.  }
26.  LOG(DEBUG2) << "Calculated importance factors in " << DUR(imp_time); //switched from DEBUG3
to DEBUG2 during omp implementation
27.  Analysis::AddAnalysisTime(DUR(imp_time));
28. }
```

Figure 11. Original importance measurement calculation code snippet.

```

1. void ImportanceAnalysis::Analyze() noexcept {
2.     CLOCK(imp_time);
3.     LOG(DEBUG3) << "Calculating importance factors...";
4.     double p_total = this->p_total();
5.     const std::vector<const mef::BasicEvent*>& basic_events =
6.         this->basic_events();
7.
8.     std::vector<int> occurrences = this->occurrences();
9.
10.    // Parallelize the loop using OpenMP
11.    #pragma omp parallel for
12.    for (int i = 0; i < basic_events.size(); ++i) {
13.        if (occurrences[i] == 0)
14.            continue;
15.        const mef::BasicEvent& event = *basic_events[i];
16.        double p_var = event.p();
17.        ImportanceFactors imp{};
18.        imp.occurrence = occurrences[i];
19.        imp.mif = this->CalculateMif(i);
20.        if (p_total != 0) {
21.            imp.cif = p_var * imp.mif / p_total;
22.            imp.raw = 1 + (1 - p_var) * imp.mif / p_total;
23.            imp.dif = p_var * imp.raw;
24.            if (p_total != p_var * imp.mif)
25.                imp.rrw = p_total / (p_total - p_var * imp.mif);
26.        }
27.
28.    #pragma omp critical
29.        importance_.push_back({event, imp});
30.    }
31.
32.    LOG(DEBUG2) << "Calculated importance factors in " << DUR(imp_time); //switched from DEBUG3
to DEBUG2 during omp implementation
33.    Analysis::AddAnalysisTime(DUR(imp_time));
34. }

```

Figure 12. Revised (parallelized) importance measurement calculation code snippet.

```

1. std::vector<double> UncertaintyAnalyzer<Calculator>::Sample() noexcept {
2.     std::vector<std::pair<int, mef::Expression&>> deviate_expressions =
3.         UncertaintyAnalysis::GatherDeviateExpressions(prob_analyzer_->graph());
4.     Pdag::IndexMap<double> p_vars = prob_analyzer_->p_vars(); // Private copy!
5.     std::vector<double> samples;
6.     samples.reserve(Analysis::settings().num_trials());
7.
8.     for (int i = 0; i < Analysis::settings().num_trials(); ++i) {
9.         UncertaintyAnalysis::SampleExpressions(deviate_expressions, &p_vars);
10.        double result = prob_analyzer_->CalculateTotalProbability(p_vars);
11.        assert(result >= 0 && result <= 1);
12.        samples.push_back(result);
13.    }
14.
15.    return samples;
16. }

```

Figure 13. Original uncertainty calculation code snippet.

```

1. std::vector<double> UncertaintyAnalyzer<Calculator>::Sample() noexcept {
2.     std::vector<std::pair<int, mef::Expression&>> deviate_expressions =
3.         UncertaintyAnalysis::GatherDeviateExpressions(prob_analyzer_->graph());
4.     Pdag::IndexMap<double> p_vars = prob_analyzer_->p_vars(); // Private copy!
5.     std::vector<double> samples;
6.     samples.reserve(Analysis::settings().num_trials());
7.
8.     #pragma omp parallel
9.     {
10.        std::vector<double> thread_samples;
11.        thread_samples.reserve(Analysis::settings().num_trials() / omp_get_num_threads());
12.
13.        #pragma omp for
14.        for (int i = 0; i < Analysis::settings().num_trials(); ++i) {
15.            UncertaintyAnalysis::SampleExpressions(deviate_expressions, &p_vars);
16.            double result = prob_analyzer_->CalculateTotalProbability(p_vars);
17.            assert(result >= 0 && result <= 1);
18.            thread_samples.push_back(result);
19.        }
20.
21.        #pragma omp critical
22.        {
23.            samples.insert(samples.end(), thread_samples.begin(), thread_samples.end());
24.        }
25.    }
26.
27.    return samples;
28. }

```

Figure 14. Revised (parallelized) uncertainty calculation code snippet.

With a 12-core CPU, speedups of up to 5.98 times for importance measurement (edfpa14r model) and 5.90 times for uncertainty calculation (edfpa14r model) are

achieved, as shown in Table 7. A maximum overall speedup of 5.18 times (das9204 model) is attained. Additionally, Amdahl's Law is applied to predict the parallel fraction of the code. It is determined that up to 74 percent of the code is parallelized (das9204 model), with a minimum of 31 percent (chinese model), depending on the complexity of the input model. The speedup for each revision is depicted in Figure 15. The parallel alignment of the dots with the y-axis demonstrates the speedup achieved for each revision, as well as the overall speedup.

Table 6. Summary of all runs for each improvement target.

#	Input	Imp-Ori	Uncert-Ori	Report-Ori	Whole-Ori	Imp-Rev	Uncert-Rev	Report-Rev	Whole-Rev
1	baobab1	1.22E+02	9.93E+02	1.03E+02	1.39E+03	3.99E+01	3.14E+02	4.39E+01	5.71E+02
2	baobab2	4.77E+00	7.34E+01	8.35E+00	8.85E+01	2.97E+00	4.06E+01	5.90E+00	5.17E+01
3	baobab3	1.33E+02	8.20E+02	5.39E+01	1.05E+03	3.02E+01	1.64E+02	2.65E+01	2.67E+02
4	chinese	1.14E+00	2.22E+01	8.09E-01	2.46E+01	6.28E+00	8.63E+00	8.12E-01	1.64E+01
5	das9201	1.47E+02	6.03E+02	2.10E+01	7.74E+02	3.94E+01	1.66E+02	1.48E+01	2.23E+02
6	das9202	2.39E+02	2.40E+03	7.01E+01	2.72E+03	5.12E+01	5.46E+02	2.94E+01	6.32E+02
7	das9203	1.04E+02	1.01E+03	2.78E+01	1.15E+03	2.76E+01	2.31E+02	1.72E+01	2.78E+02
8	das9204	1.27E+02	1.32E+03	4.36E+01	1.50E+03	2.74E+01	2.40E+02	1.78E+01	2.89E+02
9	das9205	8.70E+01	8.44E+02	3.29E+01	9.66E+02	3.26E+01	2.68E+02	4.83E+01	3.51E+02
10	das9206	2.44E+02	1.00E+03	3.28E+01	1.28E+03	5.87E+01	2.42E+02	2.06E+01	3.25E+02
11	das9207	8.21E+02	1.49E+03	3.95E+01	2.36E+03	1.70E+02	3.29E+02	2.79E+01	5.38E+02
12	das9208	4.89E+01	2.38E+02	1.32E+01	3.10E+02	1.72E+01	6.27E+01	8.52E+00	9.68E+01
13	edf9201	9.23E+03	2.51E+04	9.47E+02	3.54E+04	2.18E+03	6.06E+03	6.02E+02	8.91E+03
14	edf9202	1.03E+04	1.25E+04	2.75E+02	2.32E+04	2.30E+03	2.87E+03	1.42E+02	5.34E+03
15	edf9203	4.41E+05	6.11E+05	4.51E+04	1.11E+06	1.12E+05	1.56E+05	2.30E+04	3.00E+05
16	edf9204	1.07E+06	1.64E+06	8.06E+04	2.80E+06	2.19E+05	3.34E+05	3.82E+04	5.99E+05
17	edf9205	3.47E+02	1.05E+03	3.66E+01	1.44E+03	6.66E+01	2.06E+02	2.15E+01	2.99E+02
18	edfpa14b	3.02E+06	4.84E+06	2.70E+05	8.14E+06	6.47E+05	1.02E+06	1.28E+05	1.81E+06
19	edfpa14o	2.83E+06	4.56E+06	5.95E+05	8.00E+06	5.93E+05	9.59E+05	1.28E+05	1.69E+06
20	edfpa14p	3.98E+03	1.59E+04	1.04E+03	2.46E+04	7.82E+02	3.36E+03	4.11E+02	8.26E+03
21	edfpa14q	2.85E+06	4.55E+06	2.67E+05	7.69E+06	6.49E+05	1.01E+06	1.31E+05	1.81E+06
22	edfpa14r	3.03E+03	1.42E+04	9.56E+02	2.60E+04	5.06E+02	2.40E+03	3.79E+02	1.13E+04
23	edfpa15b	7.03E+04	1.23E+05	6.21E+03	1.99E+05	1.44E+04	2.53E+04	3.09E+03	4.32E+04
24	edfpa15o	6.88E+04	1.21E+05	6.15E+03	1.97E+05	1.35E+04	2.37E+04	2.99E+03	4.07E+04
25	edfpa15p	2.08E+02	1.04E+03	6.09E+01	1.46E+03	4.68E+01	2.19E+02	2.71E+01	4.55E+02
26	edfpa15q	6.68E+04	1.19E+05	6.18E+03	1.93E+05	1.28E+04	2.29E+04	3.13E+03	3.99E+04
27	edfpa15r	1.86E+02	1.05E+03	5.87E+01	1.61E+03	5.04E+01	2.84E+02	2.59E+01	6.85E+02
28	elf9601	2.66E+03	9.99E+03	3.34E+02	1.30E+04	6.68E+02	2.52E+03	1.55E+02	3.39E+03
29	ft10	4.43E+00	1.47E+01	7.02E-01	2.09E+01	2.01E+00	5.55E+00	7.84E-01	9.43E+00
30	isp9601	4.92E+03	1.71E+04	5.49E+02	2.26E+04	1.14E+03	3.84E+03	2.84E+02	5.30E+03

Table 6 (continued).

31	isp9602	8.19E+04	3.47E+05	1.32E+04	4.43E+05	1.80E+04	7.64E+04	5.32E+03	1.00E+05
32	isp9603	2.93E+01	1.60E+02	5.61E+00	1.96E+02	1.05E+01	4.47E+01	3.95E+00	6.08E+01
33	isp9604	2.04E+04	4.74E+04	1.35E+03	6.93E+04	4.57E+03	1.11E+04	7.54E+02	1.65E+04
34	isp9605	6.04E+00	9.29E+01	1.10E+01	1.12E+02	3.21E+00	4.30E+01	5.62E+00	5.43E+01
35	isp9606	1.72E+01	8.65E+01	2.74E+00	1.07E+02	4.41E+00	2.25E+01	2.14E+00	2.99E+01
36	isp9607	1.88E+03	1.29E+04	4.22E+02	1.52E+04	4.17E+02	2.90E+03	1.58E+02	3.51E+03
37	jbd9601	1.21E+03	1.11E+03	2.39E+01	2.36E+03	3.03E+02	3.05E+02	1.59E+01	6.34E+02

Explanations about the table:

- All units are in milliseconds.
- Imp-Ori: Original importance measurement calculation time.
- Uncert-Ori: Original uncertainty calculation time.
- Report-Ori: Original reporting time.
- Whole-Ori: Original whole run time.
- Imp-Rev: Revised (parallelized) importance measurement calculation time.
- Uncert-Rev: Revised (parallelized) uncertainty calculation time.
- Report-Rev: Revised (optimized) reporting time.
- Whole-Rev: Revised whole run time.

Table 7. Summary of speed up for each improvement.

#	Input	Speedup-Imp	Speedup-Uncert	Speedup-Report	Speedup-Whole	Parallel Fraction
1	baobab1	3.07	2.34	3.16	2.44	0.54
2	baobab2	1.60	1.42	1.81	1.71	0.38
3	baobab3	4.41	2.03	5.00	3.94	0.69
4	chinese	0.18	1.00	2.58	1.51	0.31
5	das9201	3.73	1.42	3.63	3.47	0.66
6	das9202	4.66	2.38	4.40	4.30	0.71
7	das9203	3.77	1.61	4.40	4.13	0.70
8	das9204	4.62	2.44	5.51	5.18	0.74
9	das9205	2.67	0.68	3.15	2.75	0.59
10	das9206	4.15	1.59	4.14	3.94	0.69
11	das9207	4.82	1.42	4.54	4.39	0.71
12	das9208	2.85	1.55	3.79	3.20	0.63
13	edf9201	4.23	1.57	4.14	3.97	0.69
14	edf9202	4.49	1.94	4.37	4.34	0.71
15	edf9203	3.95	1.96	3.92	3.69	0.67
16	edf9204	4.87	2.11	4.93	4.67	0.73
17	edf9205	5.21	1.70	5.10	4.81	0.73
18	edfpa14b	4.66	2.10	4.74	4.50	0.72
19	edfpa14o	4.78	4.66	4.75	4.73	0.73
20	edfpa14p	5.09	2.53	4.73	2.98	0.61
21	edfpa14q	4.39	2.04	4.51	4.25	0.71
22	edfpa14r.	5.98	2.52	5.90	2.31	0.52
23	edfpa15b	4.89	2.01	4.84	4.62	0.72
24	edfpa15o	5.10	2.05	5.11	4.83	0.73
25	edfpa15p	4.45	2.25	4.74	3.21	0.64
26	edfpa15q	5.21	1.97	5.18	4.84	0.73
27	edfpa15r	3.68	2.27	3.69	2.36	0.53
28	elf9601	3.98	2.15	3.96	3.84	0.68
29	ftr10	2.20	0.90	2.66	2.22	0.51
30	isp9601	4.32	1.93	4.45	4.26	0.71

Table 7 (continued).

31	isp9602	4.56	2.49	4.55	4.41	0.71
32	isp9603	2.79	1.42	3.57	3.23	0.64
33	isp9604	4.47	1.79	4.29	4.20	0.70
34	isp9605	1.88	1.96	2.16	2.06	0.48
35	isp9606	3.90	1.28	3.85	3.59	0.67
36	isp9607	4.50	2.66	4.43	4.33	0.71
37	jbd9601	4.00	1.51	3.64	3.72	0.67

Figure 15. Speed up representation of each revision.

1.3.4.2 Conclusion

The improvement in SCRAM is realized through leveraging data structure changes and implementing OpenMP. Achieving up to a 4.84 speedup in a 12-core environment (das9204 model), suitable for general users, demonstrates significant enhancement.

1.4 Benchmarks for Multi-Hazard PRA Models

Publicly available PRA models only address single hazards. However, the research community is increasingly focusing on external hazards, particularly multi-hazard scenarios, and continues to refine modeling approaches. The Probabilistic Safety Assessment (PSA) of Natural External Hazards Including Seismic (NARSIS) [27] project brought together three interconnected components:

1. Theoretical advancements in the scientific approach to natural hazard assessment and their impacts, including improvements in uncertainty evaluation and the reduction of subjectivity in expert judgments.
2. Validation of these findings within the framework of safety assessment through model reduction, simulations, and experiments.
3. Application of the outcomes at the demonstration level, providing tools to support severe accident management.

Additionally, to evaluate multi-hazard risks in an integrated manner for the operating nuclear fleet, Idaho National Laboratory (INL) led the Risk Informed Safety Margins Characterization (RISMC) [28] project. As a follow-up, seismic and flooding phenomena for a generic PWR model [29] were published. However, these efforts primarily focused on the dynamic nature of external hazards and conducted extensive work on determining basic event failure probabilities within these dynamics, without directly addressing the quantification problem.

As part of our ongoing work, an open-source code was developed to create multi-hazard logic [30] for given scenarios. These development efforts were carried out in collaboration with INL, resulting in various outcomes [31], [32], [33].

To improve the quantification step by evaluating exact probabilities in multi-hazard PRA models, we proposed a PRA model pre-processor, as outlined in Milestone Report 2. This pre-processor enables multi-hazard models to be efficiently solved by sorting and distributing them across threads, with the logic summarized in Figure 16.

A PRA model consists of multiple text files that describe the model's logic and the failure data for its basic events. Before passing these files to the quantification engine, our pre-processor parses the text files and gathers all failure probabilities. We define a truncation

probability of 0.5. If more than 50% of the failure probabilities are below this threshold, the model is solved using the MOCUS MCUB method. Otherwise, the BDD method is used for exact quantification. This approach ensures accurate results, particularly for models with higher failure probabilities, and minimizes overestimation.

1. Parse given input files
2. Gather all failure probabilities for basic events
3. Create a dictionary for each input file as a key, failure probabilities as a value
4. Set threshold for a basic event failure probability value
5. Count how many failure probabilities are less than the predetermined threshold value
6. If more than the predefined percentage of failure probabilities is less than the predetermined threshold value
7. Then, solve the model using `mocus mcub`
8. Else solve model using `bdd`

Figure 16. Pseudocode for demonstrated PRA model pre-processor.

Additionally, the pre-processor offers a threading option to significantly speed up calculations by solving models in parallel on a single computer. For testing purposes, various fault tree models were created in different configurations and are publicly available through a repository [34]. While the logic remains the same across configurations, the probability ranges of the basic events were adjusted to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed truncation threshold and its application.

1.5 Conclusion and Alignment to Project Goals

Improvement strategy culminates in significant enhancements to a PRA tool, as evidenced by the results summarized in Figure 17. The improvement strategy encompasses various aspects, including cut set generation, storing cut sets, calculations (includes probability, uncertainty, and importance measurement), reporting results, and the development of a post-processing engine.

Figure 17. Improvement strategy of a PRA tool as a success tree format, along with current accomplishments, includes.

Figure 17 illustrates that certain improvements are applied to SAPHSOLVE (labeled as SS), while others are targeted at SCRAM (labeled as S). For SAPHSOLVE, notable achievements include a speedup of up to 1.67 times in the cut set generation step, along with the creation and testing of a new post-processing engine.

In the case of SCRAM, optimization efforts focus on cut set storage through the adoption of a new data structure, followed by improvements in probability calculation leveraging the new data structure and OpenMP implementation. Although the overall contribution from the probability calculation revision may not be significant, it lays the groundwork for future implementations such as the post-processing engine. Additionally, enhancements in uncertainty calculation and importance measurement are achieved through OpenMP implementation.

The enhancement framework established here serves as a foundational blueprint for improving all PRA tools. Moreover, this work sets a benchmark for PRA tool developers in terms of code, solution, and model verification.

The previously demonstrated PRA model pre-processor is capable of managing solvers to solve models efficiently in a shorter time that include multi-hazard scenarios. As future work, this approach will be tested against actual models to verify the findings observed in synthetic models.

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3 Appendices

3.1 Appendix A: ACC JSCUTIN File from Generic PWR Model

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608.     },
609.     "value": 1.00000E+00,
610.     "initf": " ",
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626. },
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633.     "mt": 1
634.   },
635.   "value": 2.01600E-07,
636.   "initf": " ",
637.   "processf": " ",
638.   "calctype": "3"
639. },
640. {
641.   "id": "110",
642.   "corrgate": "0",
643.   "name": "ACC-TNK-LK-ACCD",
644.   "evworkspacepair": {
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646.     "mt": 1
647.   },
648.   "value": 2.88000E-06,
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652. },
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654.   "id": "111",
655.   "corrgate": "0",
656.   "name": "ACC-TNK-FC-ACCD",
657.   "evworkspacepair": {
658.     "ph": 1,
659.     "mt": 1
660.   },
661.   "value": 4.60800E-06,
662.   "initf": " ",
663.   "processf": " ",
664.   "calctype": "3"
665. },
666. {
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669.     "name": "RCS-LOCA-CL1",
670.     "evworkspacepair": {
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672.         "mt": 1
673.     },
674.     "value": 2.50000E-01,
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715.     "processf": " ",
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717. },
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721.     "name": "RCS-CKV-CC-001",
722.     "evworkspacepair": {
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727.   "initf": " ",
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752.   "value": 9.24000E-06,
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754.   "processf": " ",
755.   "calctype": "1"
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758.   "id": "2903",
759.   "corrgate": "0",
760.   "name": "RCS-CKV-CC-004",
761.   "evworkspacepair": {
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763.     "mt": 1
764.   },
765.   "value": 9.24000E-06,
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767.   "processf": " ",
768.   "calctype": "1"
769. },
770. {
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772.   "corrgate": "0",
773.   "name": "RCS-CKV-CF-CC",
774.   "evworkspacepair": {
775.     "ph": 1,
776.     "mt": 1
777.   },
778.   "value": 1.21400E-07,
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785.   "corrgate": "0",
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791.   "value": 9.24000E-06,
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806.   "processf": " ",
807.   "calctype": "1"
808. },
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810.   "id": "3421",
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812.   "name": "ACC-CKV-CC-001C",
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833.   "calctype": "1"
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854.      "mt": 1
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856.    "value": 7.77600E-07,
857.    "initf": " ",
858.    "processf": " ",
859.    "calctype": "3"
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864.    "name": "ACC-MOV-OC-002B",
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869.    "value": 7.77600E-07,
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871.    "processf": " ",
872.    "calctype": "3"
873.  },
874.  {
875.    "id": "3428",
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877.    "name": "ACC-MOV-OC-002C",
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880.      "mt": 1
881.    },
882.    "value": 7.77600E-07,
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884.    "processf": " ",
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889.    "corrgate": "0",
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909.   "initf": " ",
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917.   "evworkspacepair": {
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919.     "mt": 1
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921.   "value": 2.01600E-07,
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932.     "mt": 1
933.   },
934.   "value": 2.01600E-07,
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943.   "evworkspacepair": {
944.     "ph": 1,
945.     "mt": 1
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967.     "corrgate": "0",
968.     "name": "ACC-TNK-LK-ACCC",
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971.       "mt": 1
972.     },
973.     "value": 2.88000E-06,
974.     "initf": " ",
975.     "processf": " ",
976.     "calctype": "3"
977.   },
978.   {
979.     "id": "3438",
980.     "corrgate": "0",
981.     "name": "ACC-TNK-FC-ACCA",
982.     "evworkspacepair": {
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984.       "mt": 1
985.     },
986.     "value": 4.60800E-06,
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988.     "processf": " ",
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993.     "corrgate": "0",
994.     "name": "ACC-TNK-FC-ACCB",
995.     "evworkspacepair": {
996.       "ph": 1,
997.       "mt": 1
998.     },
999.     "value": 4.60800E-06,
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1001.    "processf": " ",
1002.    "calctype": "3"
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1010.         "mt": 1
1011.       },
1012.       "value": 4.60800E-06,
1013.       "initf": " ",
1014.       "processf": " ",
1015.       "calctype": "3"
1016.     }
1017.   ]
1018. }
1019. }
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3.2 Appendix B: ACC Post-Processed JSCUTIN File from Generic PWR Model

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1. {
2.   "version": "1.0",
3.   "saphireresults": {
4.     "projectpath": "\\C:\\Users\\ARASEM\\Desktop\\SAPHIRE\\G-PWR Model V1.2\\",
5.     "resulttype": "faulttree",
6.     "resulttreeid": 51,
7.     "initevent": 0,
8.     "truncparam": {
9.       "ettruncopt": "NormalProbCutOff",
10.      "fttruncopt": "GlobalProbCutOff",
11.      "sizeopt": "ENoTrunc",
12.      "ettruncval": 1.000E-13,
13.      "fttruncval": 1.000E-10,
14.      "sizeval": 99,
15.      "transrepl": false,
16.      "transzones": false,
17.      "translevel": 0,
18.      "usedual": false,
19.      "dualcutoff": 0.000E+00
20.    },
21.    "workspacepair": [
22.      {
23.        "ph": 1,
24.        "mt": 1
25.      }
26.    ],
27.    "flagnum": 0,
28.    "numcutsets": 2,
29.    "valcutsets": 2.42800E-07,
30.    "cutsetlist": [
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32.        "event": [
33.          33819496
34.        ]
35.      },
36.      {
37.        "event": [
38.          33820000
39.        ]
40.      }
41.    ],
42.    "eventlist": [
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45.        "corrgate": "0",
46.        "name": "<TRUE>",
47.        "evworkspacepair": {
48.          "ph": 1,
49.          "mt": 1
50.        },
51.        "value": 1.00000E+00,
52.        "initf": " ",
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59.   "name": "<FALSE>",
60.   "evworkspacepair": {
61.     "ph": 1,
62.     "mt": 1
63.   },
64.   "value": 0.00000E+00,
65.   "initf": " ",
66.   "processf": " ",
67.   "calctype": "1"
68. },
69. {
70.   "id": "15",
71.   "corrgate": "0",
72.   "name": "<PASS>",
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74.     "ph": 1,
75.     "mt": 1
76.   },
77.   "value": 1.00000E+00,
78.   "initf": " ",
79.   "processf": " ",
80.   "calctype": "1"
81. },
82. {
83.   "id": "81",
84.   "corrgate": "0",
85.   "name": "ACC-FT",
86.   "evworkspacepair": {
87.     "ph": 1,
88.     "mt": 1
89.   },
90.   "value": 1.00000E+00,
91.   "initf": " ",
92.   "processf": " ",
93.   "calctype": "1"
94. },
95. {
96.   "id": "2920",
97.   "corrgate": "0",
98.   "name": "RCS-CKV-CF-CC",
99.   "evworkspacepair": {
100.    "ph": 1,
101.    "mt": 1
102.  },
103.  "value": 1.21400E-07,
104.  "initf": " ",
105.  "processf": " ",
106.  "calctype": "R"
107. },
108. {
```

```
109.     "id": "3424",
110.     "corrgate": "0",
111.     "name": "ACC-CKV-CF-CC001",
112.     "evworkspacepair": {
113.         "ph": 1,
114.         "mt": 1
115.     },
116.     "value": 1.21400E-07,
117.     "initf": " ",
118.     "processf": " ",
119.     "calctype": "R"
120.     }
121. ]
122. }
123. }
```

3.3 Appendix C: Rule File from Generic PWR Model

```
1. | TECH SPEC DISALLOWED TEST AND MAINTENANCE EVENTS
2. | THAT NEED TO BE REMOVED FROM THE CUT SETS.
3. |
4. IF (AFW-MDP-TM-A * AFW-TDP-TM-TDP +
5. AFW-MDP-TM-B * AFW-TDP-TM-TDP +
6. AFW-TDP-TM-TDP * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA +
7. AFW-TDP-TM-TDP * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB +
8. AFW-MDP-TM-A * AFW-MDP-TM-B +
9. AFW-MDP-TM-A * SIS-MDP-TM-01B +
10. AFW-MDP-TM-A * CVC-MDP-TM-001B +
11. AFW-MDP-TM-A * LPI-MDP-TM-1B +
12. AFW-MDP-TM-A * CCW-MDP-TM-1B +
13. AFW-MDP-TM-A * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB +
14. AFW-MDP-TM-A * DCP-BCH-TM-B01 +
15. AFW-MDP-TM-A * SWS-MDP-TM-1B +
16. AFW-MDP-TM-B * SIS-MDP-TM-01A +
17. SIS-MDP-TM-01A * SIS-MDP-TM-01B +
18. SIS-MDP-TM-01A * CVC-MDP-TM-001B +
19. SIS-MDP-TM-01A * LPI-MDP-TM-1B +
20. SIS-MDP-TM-01A * CCW-MDP-TM-1B +
21. SIS-MDP-TM-01A * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB +
22. SIS-MDP-TM-01A * DCP-BCH-TM-B01 +
23. SIS-MDP-TM-01A * SWS-MDP-TM-1B +
24. AFW-MDP-TM-B * CVC-MDP-TM-001A +
25. SIS-MDP-TM-01B * CVC-MDP-TM-001A +
26. CVC-MDP-TM-001A * CVC-MDP-TM-001B +
27. CVC-MDP-TM-001A * LPI-MDP-TM-1B +
28. CVC-MDP-TM-001A * CCW-MDP-TM-1B +
29. CVC-MDP-TM-001A * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB +
30. CVC-MDP-TM-001A * DCP-BCH-TM-B01 +
31. CVC-MDP-TM-001A * SWS-MDP-TM-1B +
32. AFW-MDP-TM-B * LPI-MDP-TM-1A +
33. SIS-MDP-TM-01B * LPI-MDP-TM-1A +
34. CVC-MDP-TM-001B * LPI-MDP-TM-1A +
35. LPI-MDP-TM-1A * LPI-MDP-TM-1B +
36. LPI-MDP-TM-1A * CCW-MDP-TM-1B +
37. LPI-MDP-TM-1A * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB +
38. LPI-MDP-TM-1A * DCP-BCH-TM-B01 +
39. LPI-MDP-TM-1A * SWS-MDP-TM-1B +
40. AFW-MDP-TM-B * CCW-MDP-TM-1A +
41. SIS-MDP-TM-01B * CCW-MDP-TM-1A +
42. CVC-MDP-TM-001B * CCW-MDP-TM-1A +
43. LPI-MDP-TM-1B * CCW-MDP-TM-1A +
44. CCW-MDP-TM-1A * CCW-MDP-TM-1B +
45. CCW-MDP-TM-1A * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB +
46. CCW-MDP-TM-1A * DCP-BCH-TM-B01 +
47. CCW-MDP-TM-1A * SWS-MDP-TM-1B +
48. AFW-MDP-TM-B * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA +
49. SIS-MDP-TM-01B * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA +
50. CVC-MDP-TM-001B * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA +
51. LPI-MDP-TM-1B * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA +
52. CCW-MDP-TM-1B * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA +
53. EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA * EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB +
54. EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA * DCP-BCH-TM-B01 +
```

```

55. EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA * SWS-MDP-TM-1B +
56. AFW-MDP-TM-B * DCP-BCH-TM-A01 +
57. SIS-MDP-TM-01B * DCP-BCH-TM-A01 +
58. CVC-MDP-TM-001B * DCP-BCH-TM-A01 +
59. LPI-MDP-TM-1B * DCP-BCH-TM-A01 +
60. CCW-MDP-TM-1B * DCP-BCH-TM-A01 +
61. EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB * DCP-BCH-TM-A01 +
62. DCP-BCH-TM-A01 * DCP-BCH-TM-B01 +
63. DCP-BCH-TM-A01 * SWS-MDP-TM-1B +
64. AFW-MDP-TM-B * SWS-MDP-TM-1A +
65. SIS-MDP-TM-01B * SWS-MDP-TM-1A +
66. CVC-MDP-TM-001B * SWS-MDP-TM-1A +
67. LPI-MDP-TM-1B * SWS-MDP-TM-1A +
68. CCW-MDP-TM-1B * SWS-MDP-TM-1A +
69. EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB * SWS-MDP-TM-1A +
70. DCP-BCH-TM-B01 * SWS-MDP-TM-1A +
71. SWS-MDP-TM-1A * SWS-MDP-TM-1B +
72. CCW-TRN-OP-STDYA * CCW-TRN-OP-STDYB +
73. SWS-TRN-OP-STDYA * SWS-TRN-OP-STDYB +
74. RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL2 +
75. RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL3 +
76. RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL4 +
77. RCS-LOCA-CL2 * RCS-LOCA-CL3 +
78. RCS-LOCA-CL2 * RCS-LOCA-CL4 +
79. RCS-LOCA-CL3 * RCS-LOCA-CL4 +
80. MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRA * MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRB +
81. MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRA * MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRC +
82. MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRA * MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRD +
83. MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRB * MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRC +
84. MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRB * MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRD +
85. MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRC * MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRD) THEN
86. DELETEROOT;
87. ENDIF
88.
89. |Remove LOCA events for non-LOCA sequences
90. if ((~IE-LLOCA + ~IE-MLOCA + ~IE-SLOCA) *
91. ( RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL2 +
92. RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL3 +
93. RCS-LOCA-CL1 * RCS-LOCA-CL4 +
94. RCS-LOCA-CL2 * RCS-LOCA-CL3 +
95. RCS-LOCA-CL2 * RCS-LOCA-CL4 +
96. RCS-LOCA-CL3 * RCS-LOCA-CL4 )) then
97. DeleteRoot;
98. endif
99.
100. | HFE Dependency Substitution List
101. |
102. if LPR-XHE-XM-RC * HPR-XHE-XM-RC then
103. DeleteEvent = HPR-XHE-XM-RC;
104. AddEvent = HPR-XHE-XM-RC-H-CD;
105.
106. elseif OPR-XHE-XM-RSSDEP * LPR-XHE-XM-RC then
107. DeleteEvent = LPR-XHE-XM-RC;
108. AddEvent = LPR-XHE-XM-RC-H-LD;
109.
110. elseif EPS-XHE-XM-SBODG * OPR-XHE-XM-RSSDEP then

```

```
111. DeleteEvent = OPR-XHE-XM-RSSDEP;
112. AddEvent = OPR-XHE-XM-RSSDEP-H-LD;
113.
114. elseif MFW-XHE-XM-ERROR * CVC-XHE-XM-BORATION then
115. DeleteEvent = CVC-XHE-XM-BORATION;
116. AddEvent = CVC-XHE-XM-BORATION-H-LD;
117.
118. elseif MFW-XHE-XM-ERROR * HPI-XHE-XM-FAB then
119. DeleteEvent = HPI-XHE-XM-FAB;
120. AddEvent = HPI-XHE-XM-FAB-H-HD;
121.
122. Endif
```

3.4 Appendix D: Proposed Rule File JSON Schema

```
1. {
2.   "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-07/schema#",
3.   "type": "object",
4.   "properties": {
5.     "generalpostprocessingrules": {
6.       "type": "object",
7.       "properties": {
8.         "conditionlist": {
9.           "type": "array",
10.          "items": {
11.            "type": "object",
12.            "properties": {
13.              "rulesection": { "type": "integer" },
14.              "conditionid": { "type": "integer" },
15.              "conditiontype": { "type": "string" },
16.              "cutsetlist": {
17.                "type": "array",
18.                "items": {
19.                  "type": "object",
20.                  "properties": {
21.                    "event": { "type": "array" }
22.                  },
23.                  "required": [ "event" ]
24.                }
25.              },
26.              "actionlist": {
27.                "type": "array",
28.                "items": {
29.                  "type": "object",
30.                  "properties": {
31.                    "addconvoevent": { "type": "array" },
32.                    "addevent": { "type": "array" },
33.                    "copycutset": { "type": "array" },
34.                    "copyroot": { "type": "array" },
35.                    "deleteevent": { "type": "array" },
36.                    "deleteroot": { "type": "array" },
37.                    "newcutset": { "type": "array" },
38.                    "recovery": { "type": "array" }
39.                  }
40.                }
41.              }
42.            },
43.            "required": [ "rulesection", "conditionid", "conditiontype", "cutsetlist", "actionlist" ]
44.          }
45.        },
46.        "required": [ "conditionlist" ]
47.      }
48.    },
49.    "required": [ "generalpostprocessingrules" ]
50.  }
51. }
```

3.5 Appendix E: Parsed and JSON Converted Rule File from Generic PWR Model

```
1. {
2.   "generalpostprocessingrules": {
3.     "conditionList": [
4.       {
5.         "rulesection": 1,
6.         "conditionid": 1,
7.         "conditiontype": "IF",
8.         "condition": [
9.           {
10.            "event": [
11.              "(AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr AFW-TDP-TM-TDP"
12.            ]
13.          },
14.          {
15.            "event": [
16.              "AFW-MDP-TM-B andOpr AFW-TDP-TM-TDP"
17.            ]
18.          },
19.          {
20.            "event": [
21.              "AFW-TDP-TM-TDP andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA"
22.            ]
23.          },
24.          {
25.            "event": [
26.              "AFW-TDP-TM-TDP andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB"
27.            ]
28.          },
29.          {
30.            "event": [
31.              "AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr AFW-MDP-TM-B"
32.            ]
33.          },
34.          {
35.            "event": [
36.              "AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr SIS-MDP-TM-01B"
37.            ]
38.          },
39.          {
40.            "event": [
41.              "AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr CVC-MDP-TM-001B"
42.            ]
43.          },
44.          {
45.            "event": [
46.              "AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr LPI-MDP-TM-1B"
47.            ]
48.          },
49.          {
50.            "event": [
51.              "AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1B"
52.            ]

```

```
53.     },
54.     {
55.         "event": [
56.             "AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB"
57.         ]
58.     },
59.     {
60.         "event": [
61.             "AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-B01"
62.         ]
63.     },
64.     {
65.         "event": [
66.             "AFW-MDP-TM-A andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1B"
67.         ]
68.     },
69.     {
70.         "event": [
71.             "AFW-MDP-TM-B andOpr SIS-MDP-TM-01A"
72.         ]
73.     },
74.     {
75.         "event": [
76.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01A andOpr SIS-MDP-TM-01B"
77.         ]
78.     },
79.     {
80.         "event": [
81.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01A andOpr CVC-MDP-TM-001B"
82.         ]
83.     },
84.     {
85.         "event": [
86.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01A andOpr LPI-MDP-TM-1B"
87.         ]
88.     },
89.     {
90.         "event": [
91.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01A andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1B"
92.         ]
93.     },
94.     {
95.         "event": [
96.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01A andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB"
97.         ]
98.     },
99.     {
100.        "event": [
101.            "SIS-MDP-TM-01A andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-B01"
102.        ]
103.    },
104.    {
105.        "event": [
106.            "SIS-MDP-TM-01A andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1B"
107.        ]
108.    },
```

```
109.     {
110.         "event": [
111.             "AFW-MDP-TM-B andOpr CVC-MDP-TM-001A"
112.         ]
113.     },
114.     {
115.         "event": [
116.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01B andOpr CVC-MDP-TM-001A"
117.         ]
118.     },
119.     {
120.         "event": [
121.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001A andOpr CVC-MDP-TM-001B"
122.         ]
123.     },
124.     {
125.         "event": [
126.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001A andOpr LPI-MDP-TM-1B"
127.         ]
128.     },
129.     {
130.         "event": [
131.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001A andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1B"
132.         ]
133.     },
134.     {
135.         "event": [
136.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001A andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB"
137.         ]
138.     },
139.     {
140.         "event": [
141.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001A andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-B01"
142.         ]
143.     },
144.     {
145.         "event": [
146.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001A andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1B"
147.         ]
148.     },
149.     {
150.         "event": [
151.             "AFW-MDP-TM-B andOpr LPI-MDP-TM-1A"
152.         ]
153.     },
154.     {
155.         "event": [
156.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01B andOpr LPI-MDP-TM-1A"
157.         ]
158.     },
159.     {
160.         "event": [
161.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001B andOpr LPI-MDP-TM-1A"
162.         ]
163.     },
164.     {
```

```
165.         "event": [
166.             "LPI-MDP-TM-1A andOpr LPI-MDP-TM-1B"
167.         ]
168.     },
169.     {
170.         "event": [
171.             "LPI-MDP-TM-1A andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1B"
172.         ]
173.     },
174.     {
175.         "event": [
176.             "LPI-MDP-TM-1A andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB"
177.         ]
178.     },
179.     {
180.         "event": [
181.             "LPI-MDP-TM-1A andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-B01"
182.         ]
183.     },
184.     {
185.         "event": [
186.             "LPI-MDP-TM-1A andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1B"
187.         ]
188.     },
189.     {
190.         "event": [
191.             "AFW-MDP-TM-B andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1A"
192.         ]
193.     },
194.     {
195.         "event": [
196.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01B andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1A"
197.         ]
198.     },
199.     {
200.         "event": [
201.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001B andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1A"
202.         ]
203.     },
204.     {
205.         "event": [
206.             "LPI-MDP-TM-1B andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1A"
207.         ]
208.     },
209.     {
210.         "event": [
211.             "CCW-MDP-TM-1A andOpr CCW-MDP-TM-1B"
212.         ]
213.     },
214.     {
215.         "event": [
216.             "CCW-MDP-TM-1A andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB"
217.         ]
218.     },
219.     {
220.         "event": [
```

```
221.         "CCW-MDP-TM-1A andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-B01"
222.     ]
223. },
224. {
225.     "event": [
226.         "CCW-MDP-TM-1A andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1B"
227.     ]
228. },
229. {
230.     "event": [
231.         "AFW-MDP-TM-B andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA"
232.     ]
233. },
234. {
235.     "event": [
236.         "SIS-MDP-TM-01B andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA"
237.     ]
238. },
239. {
240.     "event": [
241.         "CVC-MDP-TM-001B andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA"
242.     ]
243. },
244. {
245.     "event": [
246.         "LPI-MDP-TM-1B andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA"
247.     ]
248. },
249. {
250.     "event": [
251.         "CCW-MDP-TM-1B andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA"
252.     ]
253. },
254. {
255.     "event": [
256.         "EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA andOpr EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB"
257.     ]
258. },
259. {
260.     "event": [
261.         "EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-B01"
262.     ]
263. },
264. {
265.     "event": [
266.         "EPS-DGN-TM-DGNA andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1B"
267.     ]
268. },
269. {
270.     "event": [
271.         "AFW-MDP-TM-B andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-A01"
272.     ]
273. },
274. {
275.     "event": [
276.         "SIS-MDP-TM-01B andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-A01"
```

```
277.     ]
278.     },
279.     {
280.         "event": [
281.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001B andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-A01"
282.         ]
283.     },
284.     {
285.         "event": [
286.             "LPI-MDP-TM-1B andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-A01"
287.         ]
288.     },
289.     {
290.         "event": [
291.             "CCW-MDP-TM-1B andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-A01"
292.         ]
293.     },
294.     {
295.         "event": [
296.             "EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-A01"
297.         ]
298.     },
299.     {
300.         "event": [
301.             "DCP-BCH-TM-A01 andOpr DCP-BCH-TM-B01"
302.         ]
303.     },
304.     {
305.         "event": [
306.             "DCP-BCH-TM-A01 andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1B"
307.         ]
308.     },
309.     {
310.         "event": [
311.             "AFW-MDP-TM-B andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1A"
312.         ]
313.     },
314.     {
315.         "event": [
316.             "SIS-MDP-TM-01B andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1A"
317.         ]
318.     },
319.     {
320.         "event": [
321.             "CVC-MDP-TM-001B andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1A"
322.         ]
323.     },
324.     {
325.         "event": [
326.             "LPI-MDP-TM-1B andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1A"
327.         ]
328.     },
329.     {
330.         "event": [
331.             "CCW-MDP-TM-1B andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1A"
332.         ]

```

```
333.     },
334.     {
335.         "event": [
336.             "EPS-DGN-TM-DGNB andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1A"
337.         ]
338.     },
339.     {
340.         "event": [
341.             "DCP-BCH-TM-B01 andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1A"
342.         ]
343.     },
344.     {
345.         "event": [
346.             "SWS-MDP-TM-1A andOpr SWS-MDP-TM-1B"
347.         ]
348.     },
349.     {
350.         "event": [
351.             "CCW-TRN-OP-STDYA andOpr CCW-TRN-OP-STDYB"
352.         ]
353.     },
354.     {
355.         "event": [
356.             "SWS-TRN-OP-STDYA andOpr SWS-TRN-OP-STDYB"
357.         ]
358.     },
359.     {
360.         "event": [
361.             "RCS-LOCA-CL1 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL2"
362.         ]
363.     },
364.     {
365.         "event": [
366.             "RCS-LOCA-CL1 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL3"
367.         ]
368.     },
369.     {
370.         "event": [
371.             "RCS-LOCA-CL1 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL4"
372.         ]
373.     },
374.     {
375.         "event": [
376.             "RCS-LOCA-CL2 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL3"
377.         ]
378.     },
379.     {
380.         "event": [
381.             "RCS-LOCA-CL2 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL4"
382.         ]
383.     },
384.     {
385.         "event": [
386.             "RCS-LOCA-CL3 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL4"
387.         ]
388.     },
```

```

389.     {
390.         "event": [
391.             "MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRA andOpr MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRB"
392.         ]
393.     },
394.     {
395.         "event": [
396.             "MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRA andOpr MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRC"
397.         ]
398.     },
399.     {
400.         "event": [
401.             "MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRA andOpr MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRD"
402.         ]
403.     },
404.     {
405.         "event": [
406.             "MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRB andOpr MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRC"
407.         ]
408.     },
409.     {
410.         "event": [
411.             "MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRB andOpr MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRD"
412.         ]
413.     },
414.     {
415.         "event": [
416.             "MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRC andOpr MSS-SYS-RF-SGTRD)"
417.         ]
418.     }
419. ],
420. "actionlist": [
421.     " DELETEROOT;"
422. ]
423. },
424. {
425.     "rulesection": 1,
426.     "conditionid": 2,
427.     "conditiontype": "IF",
428.     "condition": [
429.         {
430.             "event": [
431.                 "(~IE-LLOCA"
432.             ]
433.         },
434.         {
435.             "event": [
436.                 "~IE-MLOCA"
437.             ]
438.         },
439.         {
440.             "event": [
441.                 "~IE-SLOCA) andOpr \n( RCS-LOCA-CL1 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL2"
442.             ]
443.         },
444.         {

```

```

445.         "event": [
446.             "RCS-LOCA-CL1 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL3"
447.         ]
448.     },
449.     {
450.         "event": [
451.             "RCS-LOCA-CL1 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL4"
452.         ]
453.     },
454.     {
455.         "event": [
456.             "RCS-LOCA-CL2 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL3"
457.         ]
458.     },
459.     {
460.         "event": [
461.             "RCS-LOCA-CL2 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL4"
462.         ]
463.     },
464.     {
465.         "event": [
466.             "RCS-LOCA-CL3 andOpr RCS-LOCA-CL4 ))"
467.         ]
468.     }
469. ],
470. "actionlist": [
471.     " DELETEROOT;"
472. ]
473. },
474. {
475.     "rulesection": 1,
476.     "conditionid": 3,
477.     "conditiontype": "IF",
478.     "condition": [
479.         {
480.             "event": [
481.                 "LPR-XHE-XM-RC andOpr HPR-XHE-XM-RC"
482.             ]
483.         }
484.     ],
485.     "actionlist": [
486.         " DELETEEVENT = HPR-XHE-XM-RC;\n  ADDEVENT = HPR-XHE-XM-RC-H-CD;\n"
487.     ]
488. },
489. {
490.     "rulesection": 1,
491.     "conditionid": 3,
492.     "conditiontype": "ELSEIF",
493.     "condition": [
494.         {
495.             "event": [
496.                 "OPR-XHE-XM-RSSDEP andOpr LPR-XHE-XM-RC"
497.             ]
498.         }
499.     ],
500.     "actionlist": [

```

```

501.         "   DELETEEVENT = LPR-XHE-XM-RC;\n   ADDEVENT = LPR-XHE-XM-RC-H-LD;\n"
502.     ]
503. },
504. {
505.     "rulesection": 1,
506.     "conditionid": 3,
507.     "conditiontype": "ELSEIF",
508.     "condition": [
509.         {
510.             "event": [
511.                 "EPS-XHE-XM-SBODG andOpr OPR-XHE-XM-RSSDEP"
512.             ]
513.         }
514.     ],
515.     "actionlist": [
516.         "   DELETEEVENT = OPR-XHE-XM-RSSDEP;\n   ADDEVENT = OPR-XHE-XM-RSSDEP-H-LD;\n"
517.     ]
518. },
519. {
520.     "rulesection": 1,
521.     "conditionid": 3,
522.     "conditiontype": "ELSEIF",
523.     "condition": [
524.         {
525.             "event": [
526.                 "MFW-XHE-XM-ERROR andOpr CVC-XHE-XM-BORATION"
527.             ]
528.         }
529.     ],
530.     "actionlist": [
531.         "   DELETEEVENT = CVC-XHE-XM-BORATION;\n   ADDEVENT = CVC-XHE-XM-BORATION-H-LD;\n"
532.     ]
533. },
534. {
535.     "rulesection": 1,
536.     "conditionid": 3,
537.     "conditiontype": "ELSEIF",
538.     "condition": [
539.         {
540.             "event": [
541.                 "MFW-XHE-XM-ERROR andOpr HPI-XHE-XM-FAB"
542.             ]
543.         }
544.     ],
545.     "actionlist": [
546.         "   DELETEEVENT = HPI-XHE-XM-FAB;\n   ADDEVENT = HPI-XHE-XM-FAB-H-HD;\n   "
547.     ]
548. }
549. ]
550. }

```

3.6 Appendix F: Code Snippets of the Test Files and Coverage Results

The following code snippets provide a few unit tests for the `quantification controller` file:

```
1. import type { Server } from "net";
2. import { Test, TestingModule } from "@nestjs/testing";
3. import { INestApplication, InternalServerErrorException, NotFoundException } from
"@nestjs/common";
4. import request from "supertest";
5. import { ScramController } from "../../src/quantification/controllers/scram.controller";
6. import { ProducerService } from "../../src/quantification/services/producer.service";
7. import { StorageService } from "../../src/quantification/services/storage.service";
8. Import {
9.   InvalidKeyType,
10.  MissingRequiredKey,
11.  MultipleInvalidKeyTypes
12. }from "../input/quantification/invalid-request";
13. import { ValidQuantifyRequest } from "../input/quantification/valid-request";
14. import { QuantifiedReports } from "../output/quantification/quantified-reports";
15.
16. /**
17.  * End-to-end tests for the ScramController.
18.  *
19.  * These tests cover the following cases:
20.  *
21.  * POST /scram:
22.  * - Should return 201 Created response when the request body is valid.
23.  * - Should return 400 Bad Request when a key in the request body has the wrong type.
24.  * - Should return 400 Bad Request when multiple keys in the request body have the wrong types.
25.  * - Should return 400 Bad Request when the request body is missing a required key.
26.  * TODO: Should return 400 Bad Request when the request body contains an additional key.
27.  * - Should return 500 Internal Server Error when the service throws an error.
28.  *
29.  * GET /scram:
30.  * - Should return 200 OK response if the service is able to retrieve the list of quantified
reports.
31.  * - Should return 404 Not Found Error when the service is unable to retrieve the list of
quantified reports.
32.  */
33.
34. describe("ScramController (e2e)", () => {
35.   let app: INestApplication<Server>;
36.
37.   beforeEach(async () => {
38.     const moduleFixture: TestingModule = await Test.createTestingModule({
39.       controllers: [ScramController],
40.       providers: [
41.         {
42.           provide: ProducerService,
43.           useValue: {
44.             createAndQueueQuant: jest.fn(),
45.           },

```

```
46.     },
47.     {
48.         provide: StorageService,
49.         useValue: {
50.             getQuantifiedReports: jest.fn(),
51.         },
52.     },
53. ],
54. }).compile();
55.
56. app = moduleFixture.createNestApplication();
57. await app.init();
58. });
59.
60. afterEach(async () => {
61.     await app.close();
62. });
63.
64. describe("POST /scram", () => {
65.     it("should return 201 Created response when the request body is valid", () => {
66.         return request(app.getHttpServer()).post("/scram").send(ValidQuantifyRequest).expect(201);
67.     });
68.
69.     it("should return 400 Bad Request when a key in the request body has wrong type", () => {
70.         return request(app.getHttpServer()).post("/scram").send(InvalidKeyType).expect(400);
71.     });
72.
73.     it("should return 400 Bad Request when multiple keys in the request body have wrong types",
74.     () => {
75.         return
76.         request(app.getHttpServer()).post("/scram").send(MultipleInvalidKeyTypes).expect(400);
77.     });
78.
79.     it("should return 400 Bad Request when the request body is missing a required key", () => {
80.         return request(app.getHttpServer()).post("/scram").send(MissingRequiredKey).expect(400);
81.     });
82.
83.     it("should return 500 Internal Server Error when the service throws an error", () => {
84.         const producerService = app.get(ProducerService);
85.         jest
86.             .spyOn(producerService, "createAndQueueQuant")
87.             .mockRejectedValue(new InternalServerErrorException("Some error"));
88.         return request(app.getHttpServer()).post("/scram").send(ValidQuantifyRequest).expect(500);
89.     });
90.
91. describe("GET /scram", () => {
92.     it("should return 200 OK response if the service is able to retrieve the list of quantified
93.     reports", () => {
94.         const storageService = app.get(StorageService);
95.         jest.spyOn(storageService, "getQuantifiedReports").mockResolvedValue(QuantifiedReports);
96.         return request(app.getHttpServer()).get("/scram").send().expect(200);
97.     });
98. });
```

```

98.
99.     it("should return 404 Not Found Error when the service is unable to retrieve the list of
quantified reports", () => {
100.         const storageService = app.get(StorageService);
101.         jest.spyOn(storageService, "getQuantifiedReports").mockRejectedValue(new
NotFoundException("Some error"));
102.
103.         return request(app.getHttpServer()).get("/scram").send().expect(404);
104.     });
105. });
106. });

```

The following code snippets provide a few functional tests for the `quantification service` file:

```

1. import { Logger } from "@nestjs/common";
2. import { ConfigService } from "@nestjs/config";
3. import { Test, TestingModule } from "@nestjs/testing";
4. import amqp from "amqplib";
5. import { ConsumeMessage } from "amqplib/properties";
6. import { QuantifyRequest } from "shared-types/src/openpra-mef/util/quantify-request";
7. import { QuantifyReport } from "shared-types/src/openpra-mef/util/quantify-report";
8. import { ConsumerService } from "../../src/quantification/services/consumer.service";
9. import { ValidQuantifyRequest } from "../input/quantification/valid-request";
10. import { MissingRequiredKey } from "../input/quantification/invalid-request";
11. import { InvalidReport } from "../output/quantification/invalid-report";
12.
13. /**
14.  * Tests for the ConsumerService.
15.  *
16.  * These tests cover the following cases:
17.  *
18.  * - should log an error if environment variables are not set
19.  * - should log an error if consumed message is null
20.  * - should throw a validation error if input data is invalid
21.  * - should throw a validation error if output data is invalid
22.  * - should retry connecting to RabbitMQ broker and throw an error after 3 attempts
23.  */
24.
25. // Mock the RabbitMQ library.
26. jest.mock("amqplib");
27.
28. describe("ConsumerService", () => {
29.     let service: ConsumerService;
30.     let configService: ConfigService;
31.     const loggerSpyError = jest.spyOn(Logger.prototype, "error");
32.     let mockConnection: Partial<amqp.Connection>;
33.     let mockChannel: Partial<amqp.Channel>;
34.
35.     beforeEach(async () => {
36.         // Mock the channel methods of the RabbitMQ library.
37.         mockChannel = {
38.             assertExchange: jest.fn().mockResolvedValue(undefined),

```

```
39.     assertQueue: jest.fn().mockResolvedValue(undefined),
40.     bindQueue: jest.fn().mockResolvedValue(undefined),
41.     consume: jest.fn().mockImplementation((queue: string, onMessage: (msg: ConsumeMessage |
null) => void) => {
42.         onMessage({ content: Buffer.from(JSON.stringify(ValidQuantifyRequest)) } as
ConsumeMessage);
43.     }),
44.     ack: jest.fn().mockResolvedValue(undefined),
45.     nack: jest.fn().mockResolvedValue(undefined),
46. };
47.
48. // Mock the connection method of the RabbitMQ library.
49. mockConnection = {
50.     createChannel: jest.fn().mockResolvedValue(mockChannel),
51. };
52.
53. // Mock the RabbitMQ connect method.
54. (amqp.connect as jest.Mock).mockResolvedValue(mockConnection);
55.
56. // Create the testing module.
57. const module: TestingModule = await Test.createTestingModule({
58.     providers: [
59.         ConsumerService,
60.         {
61.             provide: ConfigService,
62.             useValue: {
63.                 get: jest.fn((key: string) => {
64.                     switch (key) {
65.                         case "RABBITMQ_URL":
66.                             return "some-rabbitmq-url";
67.                         case "QUANT_JOB_QUEUE_NAME":
68.                             return "some-queue-name";
69.                         case "QUANT_STORAGE_QUEUE_NAME":
70.                             return "some-storage-queue";
71.                         case "DEAD_LETTER_QUEUE_NAME":
72.                             return "some-dead-letter-queue";
73.                         case "DEAD_LETTER_EXCHANGE_NAME":
74.                             return "some-dead-letter-exchange";
75.                         default:
76.                             return undefined;
77.                     }
78.                 }),
79.             },
80.         },
81.     ],
82. }).compile();
83.
84.     service = module.get<ConsumerService>(ConsumerService);
85.     configService = module.get<ConfigService>(ConfigService);
86. });
87.
88. afterEach(() => {
89.     // Clear all mocks after each test.
90.     jest.clearAllMocks();
91. });
```

```
92.
93.   it("should log an error if environment variables are not set", async () => {
94.     jest.spyOn(configService, "get").mockReturnValueOnce(undefined);
95.
96.     await service.onModuleInit();
97.
98.     expect(loggerSpyError).toHaveBeenCalledTimes(1);
99.     expect(loggerSpyError).toHaveBeenCalledWith(
100.      "Required environment variables for quantification consumer service are not set",
101.    );
102.  });
103.
104.   it("should log an error if consumed message is null", async () => {
105.     (mockChannel.consume as jest.Mock).mockImplementation(
106.      (queue: string, onMessage: (msg: ConsumeMessage | null) => void) => {
107.        onMessage(null);
108.      },
109.    );
110.
111.     await service.onModuleInit();
112.
113.     expect(loggerSpyError).toHaveBeenCalledTimes(1);
114.     expect(loggerSpyError).toHaveBeenCalledWith("Unable to parse message from initial
quantification queue");
115.  });
116.
117.   it("should throw a validation error if input data is invalid", async () => {
118.     (mockChannel.consume as jest.Mock).mockImplementation(
119.      (queue: string, onMessage: (msg: ConsumeMessage | null) => void) => {
120.        onMessage({ content: Buffer.from(JSON.stringify(MissingRequiredKey as QuantifyRequest))
} as ConsumeMessage);
121.      },
122.    );
123.
124.     await service.onModuleInit();
125.
126.     expect(loggerSpyError).toHaveBeenCalledTimes(1);
127.     expect(loggerSpyError).toHaveBeenCalledWith(
128.      new Error("Error on typia.json.assertParse(): invalid type on $input.models, expect to be
Array<string>"),
129.    );
130.  });
131.
132.   it("should throw a validation error if output data is invalid", async () => {
133.     jest.spyOn(service, "performQuantification").mockReturnValueOnce(InvalidReport as unknown as
QuantifyReport);
134.
135.     await service.onModuleInit();
136.
137.     expect(loggerSpyError).toHaveBeenCalledTimes(1);
138.     expect(loggerSpyError).toHaveBeenCalledWith(
139.      new Error("Error on typia.json.assertStringify(): invalid type on $input.results, expect
to be Array<string>"),
140.    );
141.  });
```

```

142.
143.   it("should retry connecting to RabbitMQ broker and throw an error after 3 attempts", async ()
=> {
144.     (amqp.connect as jest.Mock).mockRejectedValue(new Error("Connection failed"));
145.
146.     await expect(service.onModuleInit()).rejects.toThrow(
147.       "Failed to connect to the RabbitMQ broker after several attempts from quantification-
consumer side.",
148.     );
149.
150.     expect(amqp.connect).toHaveBeenCalledTimes(3);
151.   }, 45000);
152. });

```

The following code snippets provide a few regression tests for the `main.cpp` file of the scam-engine:

```

1. #include <boost/test/unit_test.hpp>
2. #include "analysis.h"
3. #include "settings.h"
4. #include "error.h"
5.
6. using namespace scam::core;
7.
8. // Overloads for printing enum values to assist in debugging and output readability.
9. std::ostream& operator<<(std::ostream& os, const Algorithm& algorithm) {
10.   switch (algorithm) {
11.     case Algorithm::kBdd: return os << "kBdd";
12.     case Algorithm::kZbdd: return os << "kZbdd";
13.     case Algorithm::kMocus: return os << "kMocus";
14.     default: return os << "Unknown Algorithm";
15.   }
16. }
17.
18. std::ostream& operator<<(std::ostream& os, const Approximation& approximation) {
19.   switch (approximation) {
20.     case Approximation::kNone: return os << "kNone";
21.     case Approximation::kRareEvent: return os << "kRareEvent";
22.     case Approximation::kMcub: return os << "kMcub";
23.     default: return os << "Unknown Approximation";
24.   }
25. }
26.
27. // Concrete subclass of Analysis for testing purposes.
28. class TestAnalysis : public Analysis {
29. public:
30.   using Analysis::Analysis; // Inherit constructors
31.   ~TestAnalysis() override = default; // Override the pure virtual destructor
32. };
33.
34. // Fixture for setting up Analysis objects with default settings.
35. struct AnalysisFixture {
36.   Settings defaultSettings;

```

```

37.     AnalysisFixture() {
38.         // Setup default settings for testing
39.         defaultSettings.algorithm(Algorithm::kBdd)
40.             .approximation(Approximation::kNone)
41.             .prime_implicants(false)
42.             .limit_order(20)
43.             .cut_off(1e-8)
44.             .num_trials(1000)
45.             .num_quantiles(20)
46.             .num_bins(20)
47.             .seed(0)
48.             .mission_time(8760)
49.             .time_step(0)
50.             .probability_analysis(false)
51.             .safety_integrity_levels(false)
52.             .importance_analysis(false)
53.             .uncertainty_analysis(false)
54.             .ccf_analysis(false);
55.     }
56. };
57.
58. BOOST_FIXTURE_TEST_SUITE(AnalysisTests, AnalysisFixture)
59.
60. /**
61. * @brief Tests the constructor of the Analysis class.
62. * @details Ensures that an Analysis object can be successfully created with default settings.
63. */
64.     BOOST_AUTO_TEST_CASE(ConstructorTest) {
65.         BOOST_CHECK_NO_THROW(TestAnalysis analysis(defaultSettings));
66.     }
67.
68. /**
69. * @brief Tests access to settings within an Analysis object.
70. * @details Validates that the settings applied to an Analysis object are correctly accessible
and match expected values.
71. */
72.     BOOST_AUTO_TEST_CASE(SettingsAccessTest) {
73.         TestAnalysis analysis(defaultSettings);
74.         BOOST_CHECK_EQUAL(static_cast<int>(analysis.settings().algorithm()),
static_cast<int>(Algorithm::kBdd));
75.         BOOST_CHECK_EQUAL(static_cast<int>(analysis.settings().approximation()),
static_cast<int>(Approximation::kNone));
76.     }
77.
78. /**
79. * @brief Tests the handling of warnings within an Analysis object.
80. * @details Checks if warnings can be added to an Analysis object and ensures that the warnings
string is correctly updated.
81. */
82.     BOOST_AUTO_TEST_CASE(WarningHandlingTest) {
83.         TestAnalysis analysis(defaultSettings);
84.         std::string warningMsg = "Test warning";
85.         analysis.AddWarning(warningMsg);
86.         BOOST_CHECK_EQUAL(analysis.warnings(), warningMsg);
87.

```

```

88.         // Test appending another warning
89.         std::string secondWarning = "Second warning";
90.         analysis.AddWarning(secondWarning);
91.         BOOST_CHECK_EQUAL(analysis.warnings(), warningMsg + "; " + secondWarning);
92.     }
93.
94. /**
95.  * @brief Tests the tracking of analysis time within an Analysis object.
96.  * @details Validates that analysis time can be added and accurately tracked within an Analysis
97.  * object.
98.  */
99.     BOOST_AUTO_TEST_CASE(AnalysisTimeTest) {
100.         TestAnalysis analysis(defaultSettings);
101.         double timeSpent = 5.0; // Simulate 5 seconds of analysis time
102.         analysis.AddAnalysisTime(timeSpent);
103.         BOOST_CHECK_CLOSE(analysis.analysis_time(), timeSpent, 0.001);
104.
105.         // Test adding more time
106.         double additionalTime = 2.5;
107.         analysis.AddAnalysisTime(additionalTime);
108.         BOOST_CHECK_CLOSE(analysis.analysis_time(), timeSpent + additionalTime, 0.001);
109.     }
110. /**
111.  * @brief Tests the robustness of Analysis settings validation.
112.  * @details Ensures that attempting to set invalid settings values results in appropriate
113.  * exceptions being thrown.
114.  */
115.     BOOST_AUTO_TEST_CASE(InvalidSettingsTest) {
116.         // Test construction with invalid settings to ensure robustness
117.         Settings invalidSettings = defaultSettings;
118.         BOOST_CHECK_THROW(invalidSettings.limit_order(-1), scram::SettingsError);
119.     }
120. BOOST_AUTO_TEST_SUITE_END()

```

The following code snippets provide a few end-to-end and stress tests for the backend app:

```

1. import { Server } from "net";
2. import fs from "node:fs";
3. import { INestApplication } from "@nestjs/common";
4. import { Test, TestingModule } from "@nestjs/testing";
5. import { ConfigModule } from "@nestjs/config";
6. import { MongooseModule } from "@nestjs/mongoose";
7. import { RouterModule } from "@nestjs/core";
8. import request from "supertest";
9. import { MongoMemoryServer } from "mongodb-memory-server";
10. import { QuantifyRequest } from "shared-types/src/openpra-mef/util/quantify-request";
11. import { JobBrokerModule } from "../../src/job-broker.module";
12. import { QuantificationModule } from "../../src/quantification/quantification.module";
13. import { ValidationModule } from "../../src/validation/validation.module";
14. import { ExecutableModule } from "../../src/executable/executable.module";

```

```
15. import { JobBrokerController } from "../../src/job-broker.controller";
16. import { JobBrokerService } from "../../src/job-broker.service";
17.
18. const runQuantifyStressTest = (rootDir: string, endpoint: string, numberOfTests: number): void
=> {
19.   const quantifyRequests: QuantifyRequest[] = [];
20.
21.   const xmlFiles = fs.readdirSync(rootDir);
22.   xmlFiles.forEach((file) => {
23.     const contents = fs.readFileSync(rootDir + `/${file}`, "utf-8");
24.     const contentsBase64 = Buffer.from(contents, "utf-8").toString("base64");
25.     const config: QuantifyRequest = {
26.       mocus: true,
27.       mcub: true,
28.       probability: true,
29.       "no-indent": true,
30.       models: [contentsBase64],
31.     };
32.     quantifyRequests.push(config);
33.   });
34.
35. describe("Microservice", () => {
36.   let app: INestApplication<Server>;
37.   let mongod: MongoMemoryServer;
38.
39.   beforeAll(async () => {
40.     const module: TestingModule = await Test.createTestingModule({
41.       imports: [
42.         QuantificationModule,
43.         ConfigModule.forRoot({
44.           envFilePath: ".development.env",
45.           isGlobal: true,
46.           cache: true,
47.         }),
48.         MongooseModule.forRootAsync({
49.           useFactory: async () => {
50.             mongod = await MongoMemoryServer.create();
51.             const mongoUri = mongod.getUri();
52.             return { uri: mongoUri };
53.           },
54.         }),
55.         RouterModule.register([
56.           {
57.             path: "api",
58.             module: JobBrokerModule,
59.             children: [
60.               {
61.                 path: "quantify",
62.                 module: QuantificationModule,
63.               },
64.               {
65.                 path: "validate",
66.                 module: ValidationModule,
67.               },
68.               {
```

```
69.         path: "execute",
70.         module: ExecutableModule,
71.     },
72. ],
73. },
74. ]),
75. ],
76. controllers: [JobBrokerController],
77. providers: [JobBrokerService],
78. }).compile();
79.
80. app = module.createNestApplication();
81. await app.init();
82. });
83.
84. afterAll(async () => {
85.     await mongod.stop();
86. });
87.
88. test.each(quantifyRequests)(
89.     "should create and queue a new quantification job for each job",
90.     async (quantifyRequest) => {
91.         for (let i = 0; i < numberOfTests; i++) {
92.             const response = await request(app.getHttpServer())
93.                 .post(endpoint)
94.                 .send(quantifyRequest)
95.                 .set("Content-Type", "application/json")
96.                 .set("Accept", "application/json");
97.
98.             expect(response.status).toBe(201);
99.         }
100.     },
101. );
102. });
103. });
104.
105. runQuantifyStressTest("./packages/microservice/job-broker/tests/input/aralia/xml",
"/api/quantify/scram", 3);
```

All files

75.45% Statements 1171/1552 54.48% Branches 1713/3144 70.96% Functions 286/403 78.09% Lines 852/1091

Press n or j to go to the next uncovered block, b, p or k for the previous block.

Filter:

File	Statements	Branches	Functions	Lines
src	52.38%	99/189	32.55%	56/172
src/executable	72.48%	108/149	48.83%	126/258
src/executable/schemas	87.87%	29/33	58.62%	17/29
src/executable/services	76.78%	301/392	54.91%	313/570
src/quantification	82.6%	19/23	36.36%	8/22
src/quantification/controllers	70.4%	176/250	50.1%	488/974
src/quantification/schemas	91.83%	45/49	58.62%	17/29
src/quantification/services	83.24%	323/388	64.24%	672/1046
src/validation	75.75%	25/33	36.36%	16/44
tests/input/executable	100%	9/9	100%	0/0
tests/input/quantification	100%	23/23	100%	0/0
tests/output/executable	100%	7/7	100%	0/0
tests/output/quantification	100%	7/7	100%	0/0

Figure 18. Test coverage results for the distributed systems microservice.